

ASSESSING INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION MARKETING STRATEGIES ON SUSTAINABLE BOOTSTRAPPING HOMEPRENEUR BUSINESS PRACTICES IN KERALA

A Report

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Aithal', with a horizontal line underneath.

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SYNOPSIS OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH WORK ASSESSING INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION MARKETING STRATEGIES ON SUSTAINABLE BOOTSTRAPPING HOMEPRENEUR BUSINESS PRACTICES IN KERALA

INTRODUCTION

Various macroeconomic variables such as national income, consumption, saving, investment, employment, and so on are used to analyze economic performance. In July 1991, the Government of India initiated economic reforms in various sectors of the economy, gaining control of national income and people's standard of living. However, the current pandemic crisis has replaced revolution in the Indian economic motif, and one major upshot of this current pandemic predicament is the addition of the concept "Homepreneur," which is also considered a noun drastic change in disintegrating the stereotypes of old business concepts. In today's competitive business environment, businesses are expanding into homes and spawning homepreneurs.

Home-based businesses are now recognized as an important component of the micro-scale business sector, resulting in an increased proportion of business start-ups. However, in the Indian economic motif, the current pandemic crisis has replaced revolution, and one major outcome of this current pandemic predicament is the addition of the concept "Homepreneur," which is also considered a noun drastic change in disintegrating the stereotypes of old business concepts. Businesses are expanding into homes and spawning homepreneurs in today's competitive business environment. Home-based businesses are now recognized as an important component of the micro-scale business sector, resulting in a higher proportion of new business ventures. One of the emerging homepreneur concept is bootstrapping homepreneur business.

Bootstrapping homepreneur business means relying on self-savings and income to launch operate and grow their own startup, with no help from external investors. It can be financially challenging, but also incredibly empowering, and for many bootstrappers, it's a startup funding option of choice and they mainly focuses on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" who run online/virtual businesses. Technological advancements, particularly digitalization in the business world, have reimaged the term "homepreneur" in India. In this customer-challenging era, which has resulted in massive changes in customer purchasing behavioral patterns and technological integration, the concept of home-based businesses has reaped enormous consumer acceptance. The publicizing of e-commerce and social networking channels, has paved way for the mutation of hobbies of people into homebased businesses ventures.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

María M. Feliciano-Cestero et.al (2023) in their research study highlights that digital transformation has a significant impact on firm internationalization. This paper aims to provide a systematic literature review to analyze two decades of literature on key issues related to digital transformation at the individual, firm, and macro (international) levels and its impact on firms' internationalization process. We show the impact of human (soft side) and non-human components (i.e., knowledge, leadership, digital servitization, technological) of digital transformation that can either allow or threaten it and their impact on firms' internationalization. In addition, our findings show that digital transformation can positively and negatively impact firm internationalization at the individual, firm, and macro levels. Moreover, we review the existing theories related to digital transformation and internationalization and identify the current gaps in these theories. Finally, we provide directions for future research to address these gaps.

Albérico Travassos Rosário et.al (2023) , in their study explains how A Digital marketing allows brands to disseminate information in a targeted way towards their clients and consumers, making bidirectional communication and interactions between organizations and audiences feasible. This reality not only allows companies to pass on messages about sustainability associated with processes and products with the aim of launching trends and shaping behaviour, but also allows consumers to share their experiences, needs, preferences and expectations. In this sense, the techniques used in the context of digital marketing make it possible not only to communicate products and services but also to show that brands are working to be more sustainable and to disseminate new sustainable trends that help to change consumer mindsets. This research paper employs a Systematic Literature Review with Bibliometric Analysis (SLBA) methodology to explore and synthesize data about how digital marketing can be used to promote and communicate sustainability. In this study, the results show that digital marketing strategies contribute to promoting sustainable development by encouraging sustainable consumption patterns. This scenario is possible by understanding consumer behavior, communicating key messages through the best channels and effectively evaluating green marketing campaigns on consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions

Felicia Constantin et.al (2022) , concludes that Dentistry is an entrepreneurially oriented public interest profession that must maintain a balance between professional specificity and business sustainability. Communicating with patients is vital in a competitive system, and the dentist needs to use handy resources such as websites and social media. The aim of this research is (a) to examine whether websites and social networks are a digital entrepreneurship tool used in the dentistry profession in Oradea, a city in full economic development in Romania, to promote the profession

nationally and internationally, (b) to compare the changes made using digital tools in the period between 2018–2021 for all licensed dentists in the mentioned city (between 430–450 people, depending on the stage of analysis) using the content analysis method and (c) to identify how the lockdown period imposed by the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic influenced not only the sustainability of the medical services provided to the population but also the communication practices of the dental offices. The results of examining the dentist’s online presence reveal that there is an interest among practitioners to grow their business sustainably through a digital presence that is increasingly relevant to them and their clients, but the potential remains under-exploited.

Jin Yong Park et.al (2022) tries to analyse how can business respond to the challenge that Greta Thunberg has presented to world leaders? Sustainable marketing, as part of a larger strategy of meeting sustainable goals, is one way. It has become an important practice in the 21st-century business world. Without a healthy society and environment, economies will fail, and businesses will die with them. Thus, companies increasingly realize that investing in social and environmental improvements not only adds to their credibility; it also increases their long-term profitability. Consumers expect companies to develop sustainable marketing strategies. But it is difficult for companies to keep up with these rising expectations. As a result, there is often a gap between sustainable marketing efforts and consumer demands. Those demands can be unrealistic in terms of the cost of compliance and the time required to alter production processes. Sustainable marketing makes sense only as part of a strategy that will guide all of the actions of a business, not just product development, sales, and marketing. Since governments are slow to take up the challenge offered by Greta Thunberg, the future of the planet depends on the actions taken by companies to protect the environment and create a better society.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Home-based businesses are now recognized and valued as an important aspect of the microscale business sector, resulting in an increased proportion of business start-ups. Technological advancements, particularly digitalization in the business world, have reimagined the term "homepreneur" in India. The emergence of e-commerce and social networking channels, has opened the way for the transfiguration of sideline of people into homebased businesses ventures. In this milieu, the researcher endeavors to analyze awareness about the concept of homepreneurs, the salient characteristics of homepreneur businesses, various digital transformation marketing strategies for homepreneur business, the interrelationships between and factors contributing towards effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies in homepreneur business. Bootstrapping homepreneur business is a little explored and understood area of entrepreneurial financing that needs to be investigated in a digitalized setting so that it may become a viable

alternative for those who are planning their own startup ventures but do not have access to large amounts of traditional financing sources.

The digital landscape is moving at a lightning-fast pace. Every industry has been affected by the advances in digital. Digital marketing is an essential part of this for companies who want to utilise the power of the internet in order to boost business. The tremendous scope of Internet Marketing in USA, we have to understand that marketing through the internet can be an entirely different ball game. In fact, it is a potent combination of technology and marketing acumen. Digital Marketing like traditional form of marketing is a highly result driven and set objective practice. One can't begin a digital marketing campaign without setting the campaign objectives. A digital marketer understands the needs of the clients and visualizes their needs to deliver what they want. Taking a look at last year's figures, let's see what AdAge discovered when looking at the approximate statistics: 77% of people interact with brands on Facebook by looking at posts 17% share news and experiences with others about the brand 13% post updates about brands they have connected with 56% said they would recommend a brand after becoming a fan on Facebook 34% of digital marketers have generated leads from Twitter so as a marketing management student it's very essential to research on such an important marketing tool and study on its impact on revenue generation will help you to know about how marketing agencies performing. Thus, in this context, the researcher discovers the topic of Homepreneur Emergence, particularly "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" and digital transformation marketing strategies and how these digital marketing strategies contributes towards homepreneur business practices throughout Kerala.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Today, home-based businesses have an intrinsic portrayal in the small business sector and account for an increasing proportion of business start-ups, particularly during times of emergency/pandemic situations around the world. Especially in the pandemic scenario, where the entire high society has been in the worst situation for the past three years, it is very relevant to study those business individuals who made the best of their resources to make a better living by making investments in technological advancements in an effective and efficient manner. This entrepreneurial behavioral pattern leaves a mark on their entire entrepreneurial career. It is important to understand how businesspeople differentiated the concept of a workspace from the traditional pattern of a formal working environment while also disregarding gender, religion, age, educational qualification, and so on. When the entire country was experiencing very adverse conditions such as lock downs, restrictions on people's movements in society, and so on, it is important to know how people could generate their livelihood by setting up their own home-based business ventures, which appears to be a game changer as our economy demands innovative, effective, and efficient ventures that could contribute to the country's economic growth. This is

important as entrepreneurs are found to be better in leading sustainability-motivated value creation, compared to managers in existing firms (Cohen, Smith and Mitchell, 2008). Entities that act environmentally and socially responsible from the initial outset of business development and strategy. Thus, in this context, the researcher discovers the topic of Homepreneur Emergence, particularly "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" and digital transformation marketing strategies which contributes towards sustainability in Kerala.

OBJECTIVES

- (1) To investigate the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs.
- (2) To explore the interconnection between digital transformation marketing strategies and Sustainable Bootstrapping Homepreneurs business practices.
- (3) To develop a Conceptual Model to inter - relate the factors influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on the sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs.
- (4) To prove the Conceptual Model through an empirical study by developing and testing the hypotheses.
- (5) To update/finalize the conceptual model using accepted hypotheses.
- (6) To provide recommendations based on based on proven model related to research problem considered.

METHODOLOGY

The study is descriptive and analytic in nature. A conceptual model has been developed and based on this model hypothesis testing has been designed. This study used both quantitative and qualitative data from primary and secondary data sources to investigate the influence of digital transformation marketing techniques on homepreneur businesses. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect demographic and primary data from Four hundred and twenty (420) respondents. The sample size for the study has been fixed by using the formula since the population is infinite:

$$N = \frac{V(x)}{\xi^2}$$

Where $V(x)$ = Standard deviation

ξ^2 = mean difference

Assume that $V(x) = 1.4449$ approximately

$\xi^2 = .0707$

$$n = \frac{1.449}{.0707^2}$$

$$= 420.03$$

$$n = 420$$

By using this formula how much variation and deviation is permissible in the response can be calculated. From the probability statement the researcher can calculate 'n' which is treated as the minimum sample size which has to be maintained as the permissible level.

These respondents under the study are the "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" doing online/virtual business by using their own personal finances or operating revenue from three zones of Kerala, namely South Kerala, Mid Kerala and North Kerala districts. The study's data focuses on the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on Bootstrapping homepreneurs business practices, as well as attempting to identify the interrelationships between digital transformation marketing strategies and Bootstrapping Homepreneurs business practices.

In addition, the sample selection parameters have been updated as follows:

- 1) The entire Kerala state has been divided into North, South and Mid-Kerala zones
- 2) Out of the three zones the 140 respondents from South Kerala, Mid Kerala and North Kerala districts as samples for the study.

The pilot survey and Cronbach Alpha were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability (1) is vital for homepreneur business practices, as is digital transformation (2). Embracing sustainability in homepreneur company practices (3), particularly for Bootstrapping homepreneurs (4) who run their businesses solely with personal funds or operating revenue. can obtain a competitive advantage by attracting customers and investors who hold similar ideals. Furthermore, implementing sustainable practices enables homepreneurs to stimulate innovation, cut costs, and improve their reputation. Digital transformation, most commonly associated with the multi-factor effects of digital technologies on entrepreneurial company practices, particularly homepreneur business practices, is one of the critical happenings that explain our social and economic reality here and now around the world. It shows up in the incorporation of digital technologies into all operational parts of homepreneur business practices. Digital transformation, most usually associated with the multi-factor effects of digital technologies on entrepreneurial business practices, particularly homepreneur business practices, is one of the critical happenings that explain our social and economic reality here and now around the world. It reveals itself in the incorporation of digital technologies into all operational parts of homepreneur business practices.

Today, we may see a phenomenon known as the "digital revolution" to imply substantial changes in consumer behaviour and lifestyle, as well as the structuring of commercial interactions. All of this is due to the growing importance of ICT (information and communication technologies) and the Internet, which have altered how information and data are obtained and processed, as well as transformed how people communicate and establish relationships with one another.

Digital marketing (5) is defined as the use of digital technologies and media to achieve marketing goals. In businesses that are just getting started with digital transformation, technology is considered as a tool that increases organisational performance while leaving the old operational framework and principles undisturbed. Technology has more potential, and in its most evolved form, it can result in a total organisational revolution based on current technologies.

Digital transformation is primarily concerned with the transformation of an organisation and the activities that occur within it in order to introduce a new approach to products, customers, or services. It is not merely a matter of making old processes more efficient or effective with the aid of modern technologies. A firm places the consumer, his wants, and preferences, at the core of its operations. He also becomes a value co-creator, emphasising the relevance of marketing in the age of digital transformation. Digital transformation can dramatically increase the efficiency of a homepreneur business by automating manual procedures, decreasing errors, and increasing production, all of which contribute to sustainability.

1.1 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Home-based firms (6) are increasingly recognized and acknowledged as an important component of the microscale business sector, leading in a growth in the number of new businesses. Technological advances (7), notably in the commercial world, have redefined the term "homepreneur" in India. The advent of e-commerce and social networking channels has paved the road for people to transform their sidelines into home-based business operations. In this context, the researcher seeks to examine awareness of the concept of homepreneurs, the distinguishing features of homepreneur businesses, various digital transformation marketing strategies for homepreneur businesses, the interrelationships between and factors contributing to the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies in sustainable homepreneur businesses in Kerala districts. Today, home-based firms have an inherent position in the small business sector and account for an increasing share of business start-ups, particularly during times of emergency/pandemic circumstances worldwide. Especially in the recent COVID pandemic scenario, where the entire high society has been in the worst situation for the past three years, it is very relevant to study those business individuals who made the best of their resources to make a better living by making effective and efficient investments in technological advancements through self-financing. This entrepreneurial behavioural tendency (8) has a lasting impact on their entrepreneurial career. It is critical to comprehend how businesspeople distinguished the concept of a workspace from the typical pattern of a formal working environment while also ignoring gender, religion, age, educational qualification, and so on. When the entire country was experiencing extremely adverse conditions such as lockdowns, restrictions on people's movements in society, and so on, it was critical to understand how people could generate a living by establishing their own home-based business ventures, which appears to be a game changer as our economy demands innovative, effective, and efficient ventures that could contribute to the country's economic growth.

Adoption and adaptation to digital is critical for organizations of all sizes to compete and prosper. However, many businesses find it challenging to negotiate their way through digital transformation in order to engage with customers and have an impact online. Customer experience is crucial to digitization, particularly in customer-facing businesses such as government, healthcare, manufacturing, and retail. As a result, the major goal of digital transformation is to improve the customer experience through the use of cutting-edge technology. One of the most significant advantages of turning digital is the ability to collect metrics and analyze data obtained through digital marketing initiatives. Using these insights allows firms to optimize their plans and processes for even better results, as well as contribute to more effective and efficient decision making. Soft skills such as critical thinking, analysis, problem-solving, and self-management abilities such as

active learning, resilience, stress tolerance, and adaptability are expected to be extensively emphasized in the future of digital business in 2025. Thus, in this context, the researcher discovers the topic of "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" and digital transformation marketing methods, as well as how these digital marketing tactics contribute to sustainable homepreneur business practices throughout Kerala.

1.2 RESEARCH PROBLEM

Today, home-based firms have an inherent position in the small business sector and account for an increasing share of business start-ups, particularly during times of emergency/pandemic circumstances worldwide. Especially in the pandemic scenario, where the entire high society has been in the worst situation for the past three years, it is very relevant to study those business individuals who made the best of their resources to make a better living by making effective and efficient investments in technological advancements. Today, home-based firms have an inherent position in the small business sector and account for an increasing share of business start-ups, particularly during times of emergency/pandemic circumstances worldwide. Especially in the pandemic scenario, where the entire high society has been in the worst situation for the past three years, it is very relevant to study those business individuals who made the best of their resources to make a better living by making effective and efficient investments in technological advancements. This is significant since entrepreneurs have been found to be more effective at leading sustainability-motivated value creation (9) than managers in current organizations. Entities that practice environmental and social responsibility from the start of their company development and strategy. Thus, the researcher discovers the topic of Homepreneur Emergence, namely "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" and digital transformation marketing tactics, and how these contributes towards sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business practices in Kerala context.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Sustainable entrepreneurship is a revolutionary term that connects the concept of 'sustainable development'(10) with commercial activity, encompassing new dimensions in modern business practices. It instills the desire to create businesses that benefit both the economy and society as a whole. Technology-based entrepreneurship is gaining traction in the sustainability debate, and its primary mission is to develop entrepreneurs in Kerala who meet global standards in quality, technology, and management. Sustainable entrepreneurship is a revolutionary term that connects the concept of 'sustainable development'(10) with business activities and so incorporates new aspects in modern business practices. It instills in students the desire to create firms that benefit both the economy and society as a whole. Technology-based entrepreneurship is gaining traction in the

sustainability debate, and its primary mission is to develop entrepreneurs in Kerala who meet global standards in quality, technology, and management.

A standardized questionnaire was used to collect demographic and primary data from four hundred and twenty (420) respondents. These respondents under the study are the “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” doing online/virtual business from three zones of Kerala, namely **North Zone, Middle Zone and South Zone.**

The study's data focuses on the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices, as well as attempting to identify the interrelationships between digital transformation marketing strategies and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.

In addition, the sample selection parameters have been updated as follows:

- 1) The entire Kerala state has been divided into North, South and Mid-Kerala zones
- 2) Out of the three zones the 140 respondents from each zone have been chosen as samples for collecting the data. The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of the study are mention below.

- (1) To investigate the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs.
- (2) To explore the interconnection between digital transformation marketing strategies and Sustainable Bootstrapping Homepreneurs business practices.
- (3) To develop a Conceptual Model to inter - relate the factors influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on the sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs.
- (4) To prove the Conceptual Model through an empirical study by developing and testing the hypotheses.
- (5) To update/finalize the conceptual model using accepted hypotheses.
- (6) To provide recommendations based on based on proven model related to research problem considered.

1.5 Hypotheses of the Study

The hypotheses evolved for the present study are the following.

H1: Communication via the internet and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business practices have a beneficial association.

H2: Transparency and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable operations constitute a beneficial connection.

H3: Return on investment and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business activities have a positive relationship.

H4: Client relationships and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable operational processes do have positive relationship.

H5: Advertising on net and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business activities have a significant relationship.

H6: Perceptibility and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" ways of doing business in a sustainable manner have a positive relationship.

H7: Digital transformation marketing strategies has a positive influence on sustainable "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.

1.6 Methodology

Conceptual Model Development:

This research paper addresses how digital marketing transformation strategies can be used to strengthen homepreneur practices and assure sustainability. Communication through the internet, transparency, return on investment, client relationships, internet advertising, and visibility/exposure are all aspects of digital marketing transformation strategies (independent variables) that are closely related to homepreneur business practices and contribute to sustainability. Albérico Travassos Rosário (2023) developed a conceptual framework that demonstrates how digital marketing methods have sustainedably boosted bootstrapping homepreneur business practices (11). However, depending on the variable, certain aspects of digital marketing strategies may have a long-term impact on bootstrapping homepreneur firm practices. Figure 1 displays a conceptual model that will guide future statistical research. assessments of the correlations between these factors.

1.6.1 Postulates for Conceptual Model:

- (1) Communication via the internet
- (2) Transparency
- (3) Return on investment
- (4) Client relationship
- (5) Advertising on net
- (6) Perceptibility

1.6.2 Conceptual Model:

1.6.3 Discussion on Conceptual model to relate various factors and their implication

The conceptual model for the influence of digital transformation marketing strategies on sustainable homepreneur business practices (Figure 1) depicts how the various elements of a digital marketing strategy (internet communication, transparency, return on investment, client relationship, internet advertising, and perceptibility) are related to the sustainable business practices of bootstrapping homepreneurs. This model is based on the Input-Output model. (12).

Let's look at the relationships between the dependent and independent variables in this conceptual model. Entrepreneurs must use communication tools in today's digital age to communicate to the public the high quality of their services. It has the ability to communicate, market, and publicize

their practice while adhering to several ethical norms (13). Recent research in this area has produced promising results in terms of company expansion. Kristina Kundeliene and Sviesa Leitoniene (2015) concluded their study by highlighting the possibilities of business information transparency and analyzing its impact on business practices in terms of reliability, clarity, timeliness, and so on, concluding that these variables have a significant influence on the business activities of various organizations (14). Various digital marketing methods, such as pay per click, websites, and email marketing, can reduce the cost of business practices and hence have a positive impact on corporate practices in terms of return on investment (15). Digital marketing is one of the most recent possibilities for marketing and advertising new and existing goods and services, and it is now being utilised as a medium to reach new customers while maintaining existing customer interest. Mobile phones, social media, web advertising, SEO (Search Engine Optimisation), and a variety of other platforms are all part of digital marketing. Customers can now access product or service-related information whenever they need it, rather than relying on literature distributed by corporations in pamphlets and even yearly reports (16).

Tereza Semeradova (2014) conducted research on the impact of online advertisements on business performance. Digital advertisements, according to the study, have a significant impact on company practices such as brand image building, improved sales, broad market reach, and so on (17). Customers may easily research products and services via digital marketing platforms such as websites and social media, increasing the visibility of businesses and their practices. According to the findings of the research studies, visibility and business practices have a strong association with the visibility/perceptibility element of digital marketing (18).

Thus, various elements of digital marketing strategies can improve the sustainable business practices of various homepreneurs, and various research studies have shown that various aspects of digital marketing strategies have a positive impact on homepreneur business practices in terms of communication via the internet, transparency, return on investment, client relationship, internet advertising, and perceptibility.

1.7 Sources of data and data collection methods:

This study used both quantitative and qualitative data from primary and secondary data sources to investigate the influence of digital transformation marketing techniques on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur businesses. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect demographic and primary data from four hundred and twenty (420) respondents. These respondents under the study are the “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” doing online/virtual business from three zones of Kerala, namely **north zone, middle zone and south zone**. In this descriptive study, a detailed survey of literature has been undertaken in order to be familiarized with the various aspects of digital marketing strategies and its impact on entrepreneurs, homepreneurs etc.

To evolve an appropriate methodology for the study and to formulate a conceptual framework for the study, the secondary data has been immensely helpful. For these purposes, various secondary sources like books and periodicals, research articles, newspapers, study reports of expert committees, dissertations, etc have been surveyed. A careful survey of literature helped the researcher to collect and synthesize prior studies and to discover the important variables relevant to the problem. The study's data focuses on the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on sustainable "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices, as well as attempting to identify the interrelationships between digital transformation marketing strategies and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.

In addition, the sample selection parameters have been updated as follows:

- 1) The entire Kerala state has been divided into North, South and Mid-Kerala zones
- 2) Out of the three zones 140 respondents has been chosen as samples for collecting the data using multi stage cluster sampling technique.

The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha (20) were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement.

1.8 Population and Sample size of the study:

These respondents under the study are the “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” doing online/virtual business from three zones of Kerala, namely **north zone, middle zone and south zone.**

The sample size for the study has been fixed by using the formula since the population is infinite:

$$n = \frac{V(x)}{\xi^2}$$

Where $V(x)$ = Standard deviation

ξ^2 = mean difference

Assume that $V(x) = 1.4449$ approximately

$$\xi^2 = .0707$$

$$n = \frac{1.449}{.0707^2} = 420.03$$

$$n = 420$$

By using this formula how much variation and deviation is permissible in the response can be calculated. From the probability statement the researcher can calculate 'n' which is treated as the minimum sample size which has to be maintained as the permissible level.

1.9 Analysis of the Data

The collected primary data are statistically processed, classified and tabulated by using appropriate methods. The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement. The data was analyzed using correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, the Multicollinearity test, and Structural equation modelling.

1.10 Variables under study

1. Independent variables

- (1) Communication via the internet
- (2) Transparency
- (3) Return on investment
- (4) Client relationship
- (5) Advertising on net
- (6) Perceptibility

2. Dependent variable

Bootstrapping homepreneurs sustainable business practices

1.11 Limitation of the study

Since the study is an individual effort, the investigator would like to point out some unavoidable limitations, which have been entered into the study. This research is limited to the effects of digital marketing strategies based on various aspects such as transparency, return on investment, Client relationship, Advertising on net and Visibility/Exposure, as these factors are vital for the sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneurs business practices. The study is also limited to bootstrapping homepreneurs. This research is restricted to digital online marketing and not both offline and online marketing.

1.12 Presentation of the study

1. Chapter 1 narrates the significance, research problem, scope, objectives, research methodology, various tools and limitation of the study.
2. Chapter 2 deals with the review of earlier studies.
3. Chapter 3 deals with data analysis and interpretations.
4. Chapter 4 narrates the findings suggestions, and conclusion.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF EARLIER STUDIES

Review of literature has an important role in every research study which contributes an appropriate and solid background for the various research studies. Literature relating to various properly defined problems has been collected and reviewed appropriately. It is the summary of previous researches on topic taken up. The detailed review of literature has been done in the area of digital transformation marketing and homepreneur business practices in Kerala. The earlier studies related to topic that was found in various international and national journals and magazines, Ph.D., thesis and unpublished research work have been reviewed.

In this study, Joo Carlos Gonçalves dos Reis et al. (2018) intend to provide insights into the state of the art of Digital Transformation and to recommend options for further research. This report presents an overview of the literature based on a systematic review of 206 peer-reviewed articles. The findings suggest that managers should adjust their corporate strategy to a new digital world, among other things. This mostly results in process and operations management adaption. Scholars, on the other hand, face difficulties because earlier research may not have recognised all of the benefits and challenges of Digital Transformation. Furthermore, while the Digital Transformation has spread to all sectors of activity, there are some areas with greater potential for future development (20).

In their study article, JMohamed-Iliasse Mahraz et al. (2019) emphasise that the digital transformation of society is not a new topic. Technology is omnipresent, from connected watches to smartphones in our pockets to connected items in our homes. It connects us to a world that simplifies our lives and fosters connections between individuals and businesses. This new universe produced by and for us makes use of our data to improve our daily lives and strengthen our ties with consumption. The advent of new tools based on Artificial Intelligence, as well as some technical revolutions based on Big Data, as well as the development of the usage of the Internet of Objects, call for a deep change that will affect all company business processes. A great number of research in the sector have attempted to provide a comprehensive portrayal in order to better understand various aspects of digital transition. The goal of this study is to lay the groundwork for future studies that will assist future studies better understand digital transformation and its characteristics, as well as to establish a digital transformation framework. The goal of this study is to provide a thorough state of the art of digital transformation through an evaluation of 164 documents that can serve as the foundation for a digital transformation roadmap (21).

Marco Cioppi et al. (2023) conducted a research study that provides a systematic review of the extensive and fragmented literature on Digital Transformation (DT) and marketing by identifying the main themes and perspectives (i.e., employees, customers, and business processes) studied by previous research. 117 publications published between 2014 and 2020 were identified by mapping the DT literature in the field of marketing. A multi-dimensional framework synthesising the DT and marketing binomial has been given through the use of a content analysis process. The findings reveal two thematical patterns: macro-themes about the primary digital technologies used in the marketing function, and micro-themes about the effect/impact of these technologies on marketing processes and activities. Concerning the micro-themes, data suggest that they were primarily researched from the perspectives of customers and business processes, identifying an intriguing research gap connected to the investigation of the DT-marketing phenomenon from the perspective of employees. Based on these findings, the paper develops a research agenda, as well as theoretical and managerial implications. In theory, it is the first systematic and thematic review of DT and marketing. It studies this binomial in particular from a broad and complete perspective, providing a synergistic framework of previous research that allows for an inclusive vision and understanding of the phenomena. At the managerial level, the paper may assist organizations in increasing their knowledge of marketing areas and procedures that may benefit from digitalization, hence accelerating the entire transition of enterprises to DT (22).

In their research study, Mara M. Feliciano-Cestero et al. (2023) indicate that digital transformation has a major impact on corporate internationalization. This study intends to conduct a thorough literature review on major topics connected to digital transformation at the individual, corporate, and macro (international) levels, as well as its impact on firms' internationalization processes, spanning two decades. We demonstrate the impact of human (soft side) and non-human (knowledge, leadership, digital servitization, technological) components of digital transformation that can either enable or threaten it, as well as their impact on business internationalization. Furthermore, our data suggest that digital transformation can have an impact on company internationalization at the person, firm, and macro levels. Furthermore, we examine existing ideas on digital transformation and internationalization and highlight inadequacies in these theories. Finally, we suggest future research directions to fill these gaps (23).

Vaska Selma et al. (2021) conducted a structured study of the literature to analyze the evolution of the digital transformation area and to evaluate the impact of digital technology on business model innovation (BMI). The findings of this study show that the area of digital transformation is continually evolving, with increasing attention from scholars since 2014. The findings indicate a need for additional research in developing nations as well as greater collaboration between researchers and practitioners. The review emphasizes the fragmentation of the field among disruptive technologies, shared platforms and ecosystems, and new enabling technologies, concluding that digital transformation has impacted value generation, delivery, and capture in

practically every industry. These consequences have resulted in the adoption of a number of new business models, including those for frugal innovation and the circular economy (24).

Homepreneurs are independent and empowered by many tools, approaches, and online platforms, according to Lucina Priyadarshini Rout et al (2021). In this paper, researchers attempt to investigate the concept of a homepreneur and examine the impact of digital transformation on them. As we all know, the Indian government is constantly encouraging people to start businesses and create jobs. As a result, many qualified applicants have started their own businesses from home. Marketing, financial activities, and customer relationships are all aided by digital platforms. Digitalization has surely enriched the growth and profitability of Homepreneurs. Furthermore, it assists small business sectors in maintaining continuous sales of products and services to end users through the use of a digital platform. An empirical study was undertaken to demonstrate the impact of digitalization on homepreneurs. 150 respondents from four districts in Odisha were polled for primary data. Statistical tools such as the paired t-test and regression analysis are used effectively to examine the information trend and analyze the influence of digitalization on homepreneurs. This study attempts to provide insight into the true impact of digitization on home entrepreneurs at the grass roots level (25).

Albérico Travassos Rosário et al. (2023) show in their study how A Digital marketing allows brands to convey information to their clients and consumers in a targeted manner, enabling bidirectional communication and exchanges between organizations and audiences. This reality not only enables firms to communicate messages about sustainability connected with processes and products in order to create trends and shape behavior, but it also enables consumers to share their experiences, wants, preferences, and expectations. In this view, digital marketing tactics enable firms not only to communicate products and services, but also to demonstrate that they are working to be more sustainable and to spread new sustainable trends that help to shift consumer mindsets. A Systematic Literature Review with Bibliometric Analysis (SLBA) technique is utilized in this research article to investigate and synthesize data on how digital marketing can be used to promote and convey sustainability. The findings of this study suggest that digital marketing tactics promote sustainable development by encouraging sustainable consumption behaviors. Understanding customer behavior, delivering critical messages through the optimal channels, and properly analyzing green marketing initiatives on consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions all contribute to this situation (11).

According to Felicia Constantin et al. (2022), dentistry is an entrepreneurially oriented public interest profession that must strike a balance between professional distinctiveness and business sustainability. In a competitive system, communicating with patients is critical, and the dentist must use useful resources such as websites and social media. The purpose of this study is (a) to investigate whether websites and social networks are a digital entrepreneurship tool used in the

dentistry profession in Oradea, a city in full economic development in Romania, in order to promote the profession nationally and internationally, and (b) to compare the changes made using digital tools between 2018 and 2021 for all licensed dentists in the city (between 430-450 people) depending on the stage of analysis, using the content analysis method, and (c) determining how the lockdown period imposed by the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic influenced not only the sustainability of medical services provided to the population, but also the communication practices of dental offices. Examining the dentist's online presence reveals that practitioners are interested in growing their business sustainably through a digital presence that is increasingly relevant to them and their clients, but the potential remains untapped (13).

Jin Yong Park et.al (2022) How can business respond to the challenge that Greta Thunberg has presented to world leaders? Sustainable marketing, as part of a larger strategy of meeting sustainable goals, is one way. It has become an important practice in the 21st-century business world. Without a healthy society and environment, economies will fail, and businesses will die with them. Thus, companies increasingly realize that investing in social and environmental improvements not only adds to their credibility; it also increases their long-term profitability. Consumers expect companies to develop sustainable marketing strategies. But it is difficult for companies to keep up with these rising expectations. As a result, there is often a gap between sustainable marketing efforts and consumer demands. Those demands can be unrealistic in terms of the cost of compliance and the time required to alter production processes. Sustainable marketing makes sense only as part of a strategy that will guide all of the actions of a business, not just product development, sales, and marketing. Since governments are slow to take up the challenge offered by Greta Thunberg, the future of the planet depends on the actions taken by companies to protect the environment and create a better society (26).

In their research study, Faradillah Iqmar Omar et al. (2020) highlight that digital marketing is basically promoting the brand of business items utilizing all types of digital advertising channels as a more engaging and informative alternative. This is consistent with the availability of internet technology, which allows for the digitalization of many marketing approaches. Entrepreneurs are encouraged to make the best use of these platforms in order to attain more aggressive and inventive business quality. This study will specifically look at the digital media phenomenon, which is considered as becoming increasingly potent as an information and marketing channel agent, as well as examine the influence of its use on entrepreneurial performance. This study will look at the role of effective digital marketing in the growth of company performance in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). This study employs a quantitative method based on a cross-sectional design. The domains in the identified variables are used to construct the questionnaire form as a research instrument. The sample consists of 300 SME entrepreneurs aged 18 to 55 who own and operate enterprises in Klang Valley. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) and Smart PLS were used to analyse the data. The findings show that the business goal, product promotion, marketing

benefits, and product reputation all have a strong association with SME entrepreneurs' business performance. The findings of the structural equation modelling research revealed that the effectiveness of digital marketing had a substantial impact on business performance. This explains why the variables that assess digital marketing have a favourable impact on business performance and so aid in the construction of a more successful system (27).

Normilia Abd Wahid et.al (2022) in their study explains that in recent days, Home Based Businesses have become a trend, also known as homepreneurs. Home Based Entrepreneurs (Homepreneurs) face unique challenges and need proper strategies and action steps for their personal growth. There are many studies on the impact of social media on business performance, but not much work has been done on homepreneurs specifically. As technological advancement moves fast and changes the business landscape rapidly, the choice of the digital platforms that are gaining popularity lies within social media, which is significantly important in developing the growth of Homepreneurs. This study seeks to explore the impact of Social Media adoption on Homepreneurs' business performance on a grass-roots level. This article presents a conceptual model involving the roles played by social media adoption for homepreneurs that result in contributing to the growth of business performance. The major theoretical, empirical, and practical contributions of this study are also discussed. The findings of this current study add to the existing body of knowledge in the area of feminist studies and will also be beneficial to academicians and practitioners. Social media platforms are particularly advantageous for homepreneurs, as it is hoped that homepreneurs will grow tremendously, have sustainable competitiveness, and improve the economic growth of the nation. Keywords: Branding, Business Performance, Customer Relationship, Homepreneur, Sales Increment, social media (28).

Pooja Srivastava and Meenal Sharma (2020) finished their study paper by stating that in today's competitive atmosphere, firms are reaching out to individuals at home and generating homepreneurs. Home-based firms currently constitute a sizable section of the small business sector and account for a rising number of new business ventures. Homepreneurs in India were predominantly defined by women because, for many years, Indian women were confined by societal norms and thus prevented from seeking employment prospects. As a result, many resorted to working from home. Not only millennials, but also middle-aged women and men, are becoming aspiring entrepreneurs as a result of government policies, globalisation, and the rise of the entrepreneurial spirit. In India, digitalization of business operations has reshaped the concept of homepreneurs. The concept of home-based enterprises has transformed in an era of difficult clients, circadian altering purchasing behaviour, and customer acceptance of technology integration. This study understands and investigates the concept of homepreneurs in India. The study highlights the key characteristics of homepreneurs and their firms, as well as the extent of digitalization in home-based businesses, its effects, and a future agenda. Home-based online business initiatives are a growing yet under-researched issue. The study improves business people's experiences, understanding, and mindset for establishing and running such enterprises (29).

Bhanupriya Khatri and Hesham Magd (2023) examine the internet of things (IoT) and digital marketing as two quickly emerging disciplines with the potential to revolutionise business operations. However, in order for organisations to effectively capitalise on the opportunities presented by new technologies, it is crucial to grasp the critical success criteria that must be in place. This study investigates the important success criteria of IoT and digital marketing, such as data analytics, security, and interaction with existing systems. The Scopus database was used for bibliometric analysis for this purpose. Because few studies had been undertaken in this sector, a significant gap was studied and addressed. The important success variables have been provided based on literature inferences and practises in the field of IoT and digital marketing. This chapter will be useful for organisations wishing to apply IoT and digital marketing strategies, as well as researchers researching the subject (30).

Anjana Bose (2019) shows in her research study that women's engagement in the labour force in India is low when compared to advanced countries. White-collar employment, which most women must leave after marriage and childbirth, are a particular issue. Some of these women pursue entrepreneurial endeavours. A qualitative assessment of such homepreneurs/mompreneurs' motivations, restrictions, and success/failure yielded the following conclusions. For many years, women have run profitable home-based businesses such as weaving, baking, and block printing. Women nowadays have delved into many new fields, aided by computer technology, the internet, and improved communication networks. Mompreneurs today have children and are generally well educated. They are not the primary breadwinners in their families, but they work for other reasons such as family support and personal economic freedom. The educated mompreneurs have joined in order to put their degree to use and advance their careers. They operate primarily from cities and specialise in clothing and toys. Workplace concerns, restrictions imposed by family members, and compulsion resulting from socioeconomic condition are some of the reasons why women choose entrepreneurship over employeeship at this point. They prefer jobs that allow them to work from home, primarily for family reasons and a more relaxed work environment. They employ family resources, especially the work of their younger generation, but are hesitant to use the family's financial resources. Obtaining a loan without the support of one's family is also challenging. The majority of new entrepreneurs are first-time entrepreneurs who run their businesses on their own. They avoid hiring assistance until they have completed five to six years since it is unprofitable. A sizable number of mompreneurs sell their items straight to clients. They often reach out to prospective clients via social media platforms such as WhatsApp and Facebook (FB). They provide product data, as well as price and promotion information. If they have available stock, many mompreneurs are receptive to buyers personally visiting their facilities to verify the product before purchasing. Some are listed on business directories such as Google and JustDial.com. . For all things sold, most businesses provide clients the choice of 'cash-on-delivery' or a brief credit period. Profit remains minimal even after five to six years. Aside from a lack of marketing skills, the main barrier that mompreneurs face is the view of others as a lack of seriousness. Their difficulty stems from the following factors: (1) Capability to produce the promised good within the stated time frame, (2) Return of goods handling, and (3) Dissatisfied consumers (31).

.Dr. G.Kavitha and S. Uthra Devi (2017) define homepreneur as a business owner who actively balances the roles of a homemaker and an entrepreneur in their study paper. The vast majority of all enterprises are run from home, and this tendency is expected to continue. Homepreneurs and the enterprises they run are sometimes viewed as hobbies or part-time endeavours with limited economic significance. Being a homepreneur, on the other hand, can provide much-needed cash, flexibility, and even subsequent jobs for private-sector workers. The evolution of the homepreneur is being propelled by technology and made possible by low prices. (32).

Claudia Vega et al. (2021) note in their study that technology has changed and has led each firm to remain in the digital age. The advertising media landscape has shifted dramatically. Previously, the usage of the press and television were the most common. This is how marketing has had to evolve in tandem with this shift, to the point where digital marketing has become a valuable instrument for improving the quality of life and access to goods and services to suit the demands of the population. The purpose of this study is to develop digital marketing tactics that will aid in the survival of microenterprises in Tulancingo de Bravo Hidalgo, Mexico, as the primary tool for doing business. The scientific and technological impact is that the Internet has become the ideal tool to carry a brand worldwide since, unlike previous media, it has no territorial or cultural boundaries. A quantitative technique was adopted, with a non-experimental, trans-sectional correlational research design. The goal was to investigate the relationship between digital marketing tactics and the survival of microenterprises in Tulancingo de Bravo Hidalgo, Mexico. Digital marketing has become one of the most important cornerstones of any organisation because it provides unrivalled benefits ranging from basic promotion to increased sales. Large corporations have made digital marketing one of their strategic axes, and it is critical for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses to implement digital marketing strategies in order to stay ahead of the competition and survive. The SPSS statistical software was utilised for this study, along with the confirmatory factor analysis inference statistic and the Principal Component Analysis approach, which allowed measuring the relationship between digital marketing variables and survival. The main findings revealed that digital marketing strategies such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, email, Google profile, website, use of advertising videos, Facebook watch, Periscope, Servifast alliances, content generation, and Google Ads (33) play an important role in survival.

CHAPTER III

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The success of a new firm often depends on the entrepreneur's ability to identify and access sufficient sources and levels of capital. Without the necessary level and composition of initial capital, a company's viability and success will be threatened. Either high levels of debt or insufficient amounts of capital can result in a start-up firm's inability to remain viable and capture market opportunities. The impact of a weak initial financial structure can result in poor operating performance and, ultimately, failure. Small firms' difficulties associated with raising capital are a result of their lack of access to the capital markets and inability to attract external investors. One solution to their difficulties of raising capital and insufficient capitalization has been that smaller firms often heavily rely on debt capital to finance initial operations (34). The result, however, is a large debt service at a time when another start-up. costs are high and revenues are low. The agency problems (35) resulting from asymmetric information compound smaller firms' difficulty in raising capital. Traditional sources of start-up capital include funds from personal savings and borrowing from financial institutions. Entrepreneurs who are unable to raise adequate amounts of capital from traditional sources may attempt to raise additional capital from alternative sources. Conraionly referred to as bootstrap financing, these alternative sources of capital are often important to the launch of the new firm and to support growth strategies. Small software firms actively employ bootstrap financing as an important source of growth capital. Financial bootstrapping is the set cash management techniques or practices that affect the way business manages their assets as well as their relationship with the stakeholders (36). That is, bootstrap financing includes those sources of capital that are used after exhausting personal savings (but not personal isourcesi of capital) and loans from banks. Some methods may be highly creative (such as specialized leasing arrangements) while others are less creative (such as credit cards). A large number of firms use such financing schemes that are different from traditional methods. These methods are often important in providing the required capital base to support companies' operations and growth. However, few previous studies have examined the use of bootstrap sources of capital among start-up small firms. Bootstrap financing has the advantage of often being easy to obtain (credit cards), convenient (loans from life insurance), and with few requirements (home equity line of credit). In addition, bootstrap sources of financing commonly do not require a business plan or collateral. Disadvantages associated with bootstrap financing may include higher cost and loss of ownership control (venture capital). The availability of bootstrap financing may also result in the funding of start-up firms that are not viable. The lack of funding from traditional sources of capital, especially from financial institutions, may be a signal that the proposed business is not a good idea. The ability

to launch the firm using bootstrap capital may result in the launch of a company that has limited chance for success.

In this research study the researcher tries to analyze the influence of digital marketing strategies on homepreneur business practices in a sustainable manner using bootstrapping in Kerala. For this purpose, the researcher has made an attempt to collect the primary data from the respondents who are doing bootstrapping homepreneur business practices in and the First-hand information was collected from 420 sample respondents from various parts of Kerala.

Frame work analysis

On the basis of data collected, the data has been analysed by using statistical techniques applied tests at five per cent level of significance; the objectively collected data have been suitably classified and analysed in tables, charts, and graphs in appropriate chapters. The respondents were asked to indicate their opinion in rating and ranking scales. The higher the rating on a particular item indicates that the respondent is more in agreement on that item.

3.1 Reliability Test:

Table 1 demonstrates that Cronbach's Alpha is 0.776, implying that the questionnaire's reliability is moderately good.

Table 1: Statistics on Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items, Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
.776	.776	420

3.2 Validity analysis

The data was validated by using KMO measure and the Bartlett's test of sphericity (37). The KMO test result is 0.789. It clearly shows that the KMO statistics value is greater than 0.7, indicating that the data might be beneficial for further analysis.

To assess the internal coherence of the statements related to digital marketing strategies and their impact on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, the Cronbach's Alpha Reliability test was conducted (39).

Table 2: Reliability Statistics: Digital marketing strategies dimensions on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

Serial No.	Variables	Number of items	Alpha Value
Digital marketing strategies dimensions on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices			
1	Communication via the internet	5	.749
2	Transparency	5	.795
3	Return on investment	5	.757
4	Client relationship	5	.825
5	Advertising on net	5	.746
6	Perceptibility	5	.753
		30	

Source: Survey Data

3.3 Respondent’s Socio-Economic profile

The following table shows the socio-economic profile of bootstrapping homepreneurs under study

Table 3: Respondent’s Socio-Economic profile

S.NO.	Place of residence	Frequency	Percentage
1	Urban	192	46
2	Semi-urban	138	33
3	Rural	90	21
	Total	420	100
S.NO.	Religion/Community	Frequency	Percentage
1	Christain	78	16.5
2	Hindu	322	61.7
3	Muslim	20	4.8
	Total	420	100
S.NO.	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	198	47
2	Female	222	53

	Total	420	100
S.NO.	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	below 20	24	6
2	21-30	114	27
3	31-40	114	27
4	41-50	86	20
5	51-60	58	14
6	61 and above	24	6
	Total	420	100
S.NO.	Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
1	Single	88	21
2	Married	54	13
3	Married with kids	278	66
	Total	420	100
S.NO.	Education	Frequency	Percentage
1	Below SSLC	18	4
2	Below graduation	116	28
3	Below post graduation	144	34
4	Professional/ technical degree	118	28
5	Others	24	6
	Total	420	100

From the above table

It is clear that 46 percent of the respondents are from urban area and 33 percent of the respondents are from semi-urban area and 21 percent from rural area. The majority of the bootstrapping homepreneurs are from urban area (46 percent). It can be understood that 61.7 percent of the bootstrapping homepreneurs are Hindus followed by Christians (16.5 percent) and Muslims (4.8 percent). It is highlighted that majority of the bootstrapping homepreneurs under study are female (53 percent) followed by male (47 percent). It is clear that the respondents belong

to the age group of below 20 years (6 percent), 20 years to below 30 years (27 percent) 30 years to below 40 years (27 percent) 40years to below 50 years (20 percent) and 50 years to below 60 (14percent) and 60 and above (6percent). Maximum of the respondents belong to the age group of 20 to 40 years (total of 54 percent). It is clearly understood that 66 percent of the respondents are married with kids and 21 percent of the respondents are unmarried and 13 percent of the respondents are married. Majority of the respondents are married with kids (66 percent). It is clear that the educational level of the respondents below SSLC (4 percent), Below graduation (28 percent), Below post graduation (34 percent), and Professional level / technical degree (28 percent). Majority of the respondents belong to the graduation education level (34 percent).

3.4 Descriptive Statics of Digital Marketing strategy aspects on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

Mean scores and standard deviations were computed to assess the varying importance of different digital marketing factors in bootstrapping homepreneurs' opinion of sustainable business practices, and are provided in the table below.

Table 4: Descriptive Statics of Digital Marketing strategy aspects on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

Components	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
Communication via internet	3.4597	1.12104	420
Return on investment	3.4798	1.14531	420
Client relationships	3.6002	1.11128	420
Transparency	3.4865	1.13358	420
Perceptibility	3.4601	1.12113	420
Advertising on net	3.4588	1.12099	420

Source: Survey Data

The above Table provides a detailed statistical overview of the various aspects of digital marketing strategies employed by bootstrapping homepreneurs.

3.5 Relative importance of Digital Marketing strategy aspects on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

The table above illustrates the relative impact of several parts of digital marketing strategy on long-term bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. With a mean score of 3.6002, client relationships emerge as the most significant component, followed by transparency (mean: 3.4865) and return on investment (mean: 3.4798). In contrast, the internet advertising aspect (mean: 3.4588) is shown to be the least important feature among the numerous parts of digital marketing. This demonstrates that the most crucial aspect in driving the sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is the client relationship.

3.6 Correlation analysis:

3.6.1 Communication via internet and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

The table above provides a clear picture of the relative impact of key areas of digital marketing strategy on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. Client interactions are the most important component, with a mean score of 3.6002, followed by transparency (mean: 3.4865) and return on investment (mean: 3.4798). In contrast, advertising on the internet (mean: 3.4588) is shown to be the least important factor among the many facets of digital marketing. This demonstrates that customer relationships are the most critical aspect in driving the sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

H0: The extent of sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is significantly determined by the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies.

Table 5: Correlation between Communication via internet and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

		Customer Loyalty	Internal Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.587**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	150	420
Internal Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.587**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	420	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

The table above illustrates the relative impact of important elements of digital marketing strategy on long-term bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. With a mean score of 3.6002, client interactions are the most significant component, followed by transparency (mean: 3.4865) and return on investment (mean: 3.4798). In comparison, internet advertising (mean: 3.4588) is proven to be the least essential factor among the different aspects of digital marketing. This illustrates that client relationships are the most important factor in ensuring the long-term viability of homepreneur business practices.

3.6.2 Return on investment and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

The Pearson Correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between Return on investment and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices .

H0: The level of sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is markedly influenced by the return-on-investment aspect of digital marketing techniques.

Table 6: Correlation between Return on investment and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

		Customer Loyalty	Integrated Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.668**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	420	420
Integrated Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.668**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	420	420

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

The correlation coefficient between Return on investment and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is .668, with a p-value of .000, according to Table 3.6 at the 0.01 significance level. This implies a considerably positive and fairly high link between Return on investment and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

3.6.3 Client relationships and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

In order to assess the relationship between Client relationships and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, a null hypothesis was formulated and subsequently tested using correlation analysis.

H0: There exists a significant correlation between the client relationships and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

Table 7: Correlation between Client relationships and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

		Customer Loyalty	Performance Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.787**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	420	420
Performance Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.787**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	420	420

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 7 shows the association between client relationships and long-term bootstrapping homepreneur company practices. With a p-value of .000, the data show a correlation coefficient of 0.787 between client relationships and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices at the 0.01 level of significance, which implies a strong and significant beneficial association between client relationships and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

3.6.4 Transparency and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

The Pearson Correlation coefficient was utilized to evaluate the relationship between Transparency and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

H0: The depth of sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is substantially affected by the Transparency aspect of digital marketing strategies.

Table 8

Correlation between Transparency and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

		Customer Loyalty	Relationship Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.708**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	420	420
Relationship Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.708**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	420	420

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 8 shows a correlation coefficient of .708 with a p-value of .000 between Transparency and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. This reveals a moderate but statistically significant positive link between Transparency and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, at the 0.01 level.

3.6.5 Perceptibility and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

The Pearson Correlation coefficient was utilized to evaluate the relationship between perceptibility and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

H0: The depth of sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is substantially affected by the perceptibility aspect of digital marketing strategies.

Table 9
Correlation between Perceptibility and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

		Customer Loyalty	Relationship Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.627**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	420	420
Relationship Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.627**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	420	420

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 9 shows a correlation coefficient of .627 with a p-value of .000 between perceptibility and sustained bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. This reveals a moderate but statistically significant positive link between perceptibility and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, at the 0.01 level.

3.6.7 Advertising on net and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

The Pearson Correlation coefficient was utilized to evaluate the relationship between advertising on net and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

H0: The depth of sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is substantially affected by the advertising on net aspect of digital marketing strategies.

Table 10
Correlation between advertising on net and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

		Customer Loyalty	Relationship Marketing
Customer Loyalty	Pearson Correlation	1	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	420	420
Relationship Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.579**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	420	420

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data

Table 10 shows a correlation coefficient of .579 with a p-value of .000 between online advertising and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. This reveals a moderate but statistically significant positive link between internet advertising and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, at the 0.01 level.

3.6.8 Correlation analysis test result

The correlation evaluation of different components of digital transformation strategies and Bootstrapping Homepreneur sustainable marketing practices is presented in the table above. Pearson To ascertain the relationship between the variables, the correlation coefficient was calculated. As per Correlation Analysis, there is a solid and modestly strong positive relationship between various aspects of digital transformation strategies and Bootstrapping Homepreneur sustainable operational processes.

Table 11 Correlation analysis test result

S. No.	Hypotheses	Coefficient of correlation	Interpretation
1	Communication via the internet and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business practices have a beneficial association.	0.587	Moderate positive correlation
2	Return on investment and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business activities have a positive relationship.	0.668	Moderate positive correlation
3	Client relationships and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable operational processes do have positive relationship.	0.787	High positive correlation
4	Transparency and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable operations constitute a beneficial connection.	0.708	Moderate positive correlation
5	Perceptibility and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" ways of doing business in a sustainable manner have a positive relationship.	0.627	Moderate positive correlation
6	Advertising on net and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business activities have a significant relationship.	0.579	Moderate positive correlation

3.7 Multiple Regression Analysis:

H0. Digital transformation marketing strategies has a positive influence on sustainable “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” business practices.

Table 12: Model Summary: Determinants of Digital Marketing Strategies on Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.733 ^a	.538	.529	1.92124

Predictors: Communication via net , transparency, return on investment, client relationship, perceptibility and advertising on net.

Source: Primary Data

The above table 3 indicates that the estimation of R Square equals.538, denoting that 53.8percent of the variability in the influence level of various aspects of the digital transformation marketing strategies (Communication via net , transparency, return on investment, client relationship, perceptibility and advertising on net) towards sustainable "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities are largely attributable to "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs." The use of adjusted R2 resulted in a revised estimate that 52.9% of the discrepancies in the influence level of the digital transformation marketing strategies in the study is explained by six independent variables.

3.8 Chi-Square test

Ho: There is close relationship between digital marketing strategies and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

Table 13
Chi-Square test

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	127.016	12	.000

Source: Primary data

This test also shows that there is a close relationship between digital marketing strategies and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, as the value of Chi-square is statistically significant at 5 per cent level of significance. This means that there is difference in the influence pattern of different aspects of digital marketing strategies (Communication via net , transparency, return on investment, client relationship, perceptibility and advertising on net) on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

(Chi- square 127.016, P=.000<.05)

Table 14: Multicollinearity Coefficient Analysis: Determinants of Digital Marketing Strategies on Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.647	1.659		.995	.323		

Return on investment	.281-3	.127	.223	2.236	.009	.157	6.509
Advertising on net	.057-6	.059	.053	-.979	.009	.571	1.756
Client relationship	.955-1	.087	.648	11.237	.000	.455	2.207
Communication via internet	.091-5	.137	.073	.667	.008	.127	7.758
Perceptibility	.096-4	.057	.085	1.711	.007	.634	1.578
Transparency	.649-2	.118	.271	-5.451	.000	.619	1.621

Dependent variable: **Sustainable Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices**

Return on investment (.281), client relationship (.955), Communication via internet (.091), perceptibility (.096), Transparency (.649), and advertising on net (.057) all are positively related "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business tactics, according to the above coefficients table 4. Customer relationships (.649) have a bigger effect on sustainable "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities. The results indicate that independent variables such as return on investment, advertising on net, communication via internet, perceptibility, and transparency have such a substantial effect on the sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs. The significant value shows that all variables had an impact on the sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs. The effect of multicollinearity is excluded because the model includes all of the predicted variables, including transparency, perceptibility, return on investment, advertising on net, client relationship, and communication via internet.

3.9 Multicollinearity Coefficient Analysis: Determinants of Digital Marketing Strategies on Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices

The following table shows respondents opinion towards Multicollinearity Coefficient Analysis: Determinants of Digital Marketing Strategies on Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices

[5 point scale; 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5= strongly agree]

Table 15 Influence of various aspects of digital marketing strategies on sustainable bootstrapping business practices

SL No;	Responses	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Rank
1	I agree that return on investment influences the bootstrapping homepreneur business sustainability	420	1.00	7.00	2647.00	6.3001	3
2	I agree that advertisement on net influences the bootstrapping homepreneur business sustainability	420	1.00	7.00	1962.00	4.6668	6
3	I agree sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business is influenced by building and maintaining client relationship	420	3.00	7.00	2819.00	6.7096	1
4	I have the opinion that communication via internet is having economical influence on sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business.	420	1.00	7.00	2449.00	5.8287	5

5	I believe that perceptibility is having strong influence on sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business.	420	4.00	7.00	2561.00	6.0953	4
6	I felt that sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business and transparency are interrelated and independent	420	3.00	7.00	2769.00	6.5906	2

Source: Primary data

The above table shows the influence of various aspects of digital marketing strategies on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. The client relationship [sum = 2819; mean 6.7096] has got more influence on the sustainability of bootstrapping homepreneur business practices followed by transparency [sum = 2769; mean = 6.5906], return on investment [sum = 2647; mean = 6.3001] , perceptibility [sum = 2561; mean = 6.0953] , communication via net [sum = 2448 ; mean 5.8286] and advertisement on net [sum = 1962 ; mean = 4.6668].

3.10 One Sample T-Test between influence of digital marketing tools/strategies and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

A one sample T-test is a statistical process used to examine a distribution's mean value. It determines whether the sample mean differs from a known or hypothesized population mean statistically. The parametric One Sample T test was employed with the assumption that the sampled distribution is normal. Six study factors were tested. Digital marketing methods/strategies were employed as an independent variable to demonstrate their influence on **sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices**.

Table 16: The test has been conducted using solely T-test and neither regression nor correlation has been done.

	Mean	Std Deviation	T	Sig	Remarks
Communication via internet-3	2.12	0.793	11.035	0.00	Significant
Advertising on net-6	1.90	0.873	14.990	0.00	Significant
client relationship-1	2.67	0.929	-5.397	0.00	Significant
Communication via internet-5	1.94	0.875	14.992	0.00	Significant
Perceptibility-4	1.99	0.775	13.153	0.00	Significant
Transparency-2	2.40	0.892	-7.693	0.00	Significant

The study's findings were as expected, with digital marketing aspects such as transparency, perceptibility, return on investment, advertising on net, client relationship, and communication via internet are having a substantial influence on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. The Communication via internet (mean =2.12). This means that the majority of respondents believe that they consider the Communication via internet when using digital marketing strategies/tools. The significant result (p-value) is 0.00, which is less than 0.05 and indicates the statement's importance. The mean of Advertising on net (1.90) in relation to sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is less than 3. This suggests that the majority of respondents believe that Advertising on net influences sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. and the significant value (p-value) is 0.00, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the statement is significant. The mean of the statement measuring client relationship in relation to sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is less than three. As a result, most respondents consider client relationship while choosing digital marketing strategies/methods. The p-value (significant value) is 0.00, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the assertion is significant. The mean of the statement Communication via internet, Perceptibility and Transparency in relation to sustainable bootstrapping business practices is less than three. As a result, the majority of respondents think that all these factors have major role in selecting the digital marketing strategies to ensure sustainable bootstrapping business practices. Statement in these categories have a significant value (p-value) of 0.00, which is less than 0.05 and shows that the statement is significant.

3.11 ANOVA Test

The following table shows the test result of ANOVA analysis

Table 17

ANOVA: Digital Marketing Practices and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2405.83	4	600.953	87.318	.000 ^b
	Residual	2874.32	414	6.962		
	Total	5278.13	418			

a. Predictors: (Constant), communication via internet, return on investment, client relationships, transparency, perceptibility, advertising on net

b. Dependent Variable:

Sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business

Source: Survey Data

Table 18

Coefficients: Digital Marketing Practices and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.364	1.775		3.586	.000
	Communication via internet	0.079	0.019	0.359	3.968	.000
	Return on investment	0.458	0.086	0.435	5.332	.000
	Client relationships	0.561	0.069	0.71	8.789	.000

	Transparency	0.548	0.062	0.67	8.782	.000
	Perceptibility	0.084	0.021	0.368	3.976	.000
	Advertising on net	-0.001	0.063	-0.001	-0.016	0.987

Source: Survey Data

The correlation coefficients of the independent variables in regard to sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur company practices are shown in Table 3.11. The table clearly shows that the variable advertising on the internet has a negative link with sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, as evidenced by the unstandardized coefficient of -0.001. This shows that the internet advertising part of digital marketing methods may have a negative impact on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

All other factors of digital marketing tactics, on the other hand, are all positively connected with sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. Given that their p-values are less than 0.05, all of these variables have a statistically significant impact on sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

The analysis demonstrates the absence of multicollinearity, as all of the predictor variables in the model - communication via internet, return on investment, client relationships, transparency, perceptibility, and internet advertising - have tolerance levels of 0.178, 0.019, 0.086, 0.069, 0.062, 0.021, and 0.063, respectively.

CHAPTER IV

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

4.1 FINDING

On the basis of data collected, the data has been analyzed by using statistical techniques and tests were conducted at 5 and 1 per cent level of significance. The objectively collected data have been suitably classified and analyzed in tables, charts, and graphs in appropriate chapters. The following are the techniques adopted for the analysis of data. The respondents were asked to indicate their opinion and attitude towards Khadi textile industry in the five point scale as 1 for strongly disagree and 5 for strongly agree. The higher the rating on a particular item indicates that the respondents are more in agreement on that particular item. 46% of the homepreneurs doing bootstrapping homepreneur business practices are from urban areas and mostly from Hindu religion. From the analysis it is highlighted that majority of the bootstrapping homepreneurs under study are female (53 percent) followed by male (47 percent) within the age group between 20 to 40 years. Majority of the bootstrapping homepreneurs are family persons who are married and having kids and most of them are graduates. As per Correlation Analysis, there is a solid and modestly strong positive relationship between various aspects of digital transformation strategies and Bootstrapping Homepreneur sustainable operational processes. From the analysis it has been indicated that 53.8 percent of the variability and is observed in the influence level of various aspects of the digital transformation marketing strategies (Communication via net, transparency, return on investment, client relationship, perceptibility and advertising on net) towards sustainable "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs". The study also explains 52.9% of the discrepancies in the influence level of the digital transformation marketing strategies by six independent variables. The test also shows that there is a close relationship between digital marketing strategies and sustainable bootstrapping homepreneur business practices, as the value of Chi-square is statistically significant at 5 per cent level of significance. The analysis result indicates that independent

variables such as return on investment, advertising on net, communication via internet, perceptibility, and transparency have such a substantial effect on the sustainable business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs and Customer relationships (.649) have a bigger effect on sustainable “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” business activities. Majority of respondents think that all the factors pertaining to digital marketing strategies such as return on investment, advertising on net, communication via internet, perceptibility, and transparency have major role in selecting the digital marketing strategies to ensure sustainable bootstrapping business practices.

4.2 FINAL UPDATED CONCEPTUAL MODEL

4.3 ABCD LISTING ON ACCEPTED MODEL :

Analysis of research results refers to the process of examining and interpreting gathered information or developed conceptual models. It is essential to analyze the developed conceptual model for its use in solving similar types of problems. In this section, we have analyzed the use of newly

developed conceptual model. There are many analysis frameworks used in scholarly research which include SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis [39], PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis [40], and ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis [41]. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the developed model are listed here as per ABCD analysis framework [42-43].

(A) Advantages:

The benefit of technology is that now it can support business expansion. Besides doing business by utilising technology is useful because users can also learn technology at the same time. This can provide convenience for users. The impact from the utilisation of technology for business can also make the users take note to their accuracy that it is easier for them to make decisions. So we can take out the benefit from technology for business because it does not close the possibility of successful business for businessmen and businesswomen (44). communication via internet, transparency, return on investment, client relationship, advertisement on net, and perceptibility/visibility are some of the technology advantages.

(B) Benefits:

The revolution of IT and internet facilitates the outstanding performance of the economy in business sector, through the exchanges of information by using internet and electronic devices facilitate accessibility of doing business between companies globally (45). Various advantages of the business model must be listed under common components of technological advantages. These factors constituent attributes as business benefits must be identified and investigated. The following characteristics of bootstrapping homepreneur business practices represent technological benefits: increased reachability, higher sales and sales revenues, increased market size, and business practice expansion.

(C) Constraints:

The challenge in utilizing digital technology is the limitation of access to users, limited area access, high operational costs, lack of mastery over the management of digital technology, and lack of government support (46). Various business model constraints must be listed under a common factor, Technological constraint. These factors constituent attributes as bootstrapping homepreneurs business constraints must be recognized and assessed. The business factors evaluated in the domain of technology restrictions include automation installation costs, security breaches, and a lack of digital knowledge and capabilities.

(D) Disadvantages:

Technology can be a risk for businesses as it can be very hard to implement and maintain. It can also lead to security issues like hacking attempts (47). Various drawbacks of the business model must be classified under a common aspect of technological drawbacks. Disconnection, diversions, cybercrime, and cost are all business deployment considerations that are covered in technology

drawbacks. Commercial organizations must evaluate their disadvantages in light of the aforementioned variables and attempt to convert those difficulties into commercial opportunities in order to remain competitive.

4.4 Testing of Hypothesis

Table 19 Testing of Hypothesis

S. No.	Hypotheses	Test	Result
1	Communication via the internet and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business practices have a beneficial association.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
2	Return on investment and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business activities have a positive relationship.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
3	Client relationships and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable operational processes do have positive relationship.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
4	Transparency and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable operations constitute a beneficial connection.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
5	Perceptibility and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" ways of doing business in a sustainable manner have a positive relationship.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted
6	Advertising on net and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" sustainable business activities have a significant relationship.	Correlation analysis	H0 Accepted

4.5 RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Brainstorming sessions can be arranged at Panchayat level Or at District Industries Centre among people from rural and semi urban areas through social media platforms since most people in rural areas own smartphones these days. They can create small videos of the making of the products like making of cane baskets or earthen or clay pots and share it via WhatsApp and upload it on Facebook which would help in creating awareness.
2. Resource mapping, social mapping and historical mapping of the village can be initiated at Panchayat and corporation level in each district in order to identify and attract more people to homepreneur business practices.
3. It is encouraged to use internet marketing tactics such as SEO-promotion, email-mailing list, contextual advertising, and so on to boost digital communication and visibility/exposure rather of depending just on social media advertising.
4. Instead of relying just on social media advertising, it is suggested to use internet marketing strategies such as SEO-promotion, email-mailing list, contextual advertising, and so on to increase digital communication and visibility/exposure.
5. Geo targeting can be used to create an effective and efficient digital communication system for Bootstrapping Homepreneurs and consumers.

4.6 CONCLUSION

Digital transformation marketing strategies are based on the most frequently used internet channels, which are dynamic, changing from year to year and always influenced by market trends. In terms of effective customer relationship management, digital communication, exposure, visibility, cost and revenue management, and so on, various aspects of digital marketing strategies have a positive impact on bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. The impact of this type of unconventional marketing on homepreneur business practices around the world has been enormous. As a result, it is demonstrated that a number of different aspects of digital marketing have had a significant influence on the business practices of bootstrapping homepreneurs in the formation and development of the business structure: (1) Keeping in touch with customers via digital marketing communication techniques: This procedure can be carried out using a set of Internet marketing techniques aimed at targeting customers through a specific type of information and managing customer relationships through various digital communication strategies such as SEO - promotion, Email - mailing list, contextual advertising, social network advertising, and so on. (2) Visibility, Exposure, and Transparency: Digital marketing strategies result in the emergence of e-commerce, which at times facilitates the process of purchasing goods and services because purchases are made through online stores, resulting in cost-effectiveness and increased sales because all necessary information is available on digital platforms; (3) Return on investment: Internet marketing implies an effective mechanism for bringing the product to consumers through virtual targeting, but it is a budgetary one in use because the majority of the work is done directly

on the Internet by a small number of employees.

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Impact of Digital Transformation Marketing Strategies on Homepreneur Business Practices in Kerala

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Home-based businesses are now recognized and valued as an important aspect of the microscale business sector, resulting in an increased proportion of business start-ups. Technological advancements, particularly digitalization in the business world, have reimagined the term "homepreneur" in India. The emergence of e-commerce and social networking channels has opened the way for the transfiguration of sideline of people into home-based business ventures. In this milieu, the researcher endeavors to analyze awareness about the concept of homepreneurs, the salient characteristics of homepreneur businesses, various digital transformation marketing strategies for homepreneur businesses, the interrelationships between and factors contributing towards the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies in homepreneur business in the districts of Mid – Kerala.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The study's population consists of "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" from three districts in Mid-Kerala: Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam. In this study, descriptive and analytical research designs were used. Demographic and primary data were collected using a standardized questionnaire administered to hundred and fifty respondents using a multi-stage cluster sampling method. The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement. The data were analyzed using correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, the Multicollinearity test, and Structural equation modeling. The study attempts to test the interrelationship between various aspects of digital transformation marketing strategies and how they are influencing Homepreneur business practices in Kerala with reference to Mid - Kerala districts (Ernakulam, Thrissur, and Palakkad).

Findings/Result: Based on the analysis results, it has been found that various aspects of digital marketing strategies towards bootstrapping homepreneur business practices are having a positive influence and all the determinants of digital transformation marketing strategies are statistically independent.

Originality/Value: The researcher applied the INPUT – OUTPUT model to the data from 2021 to 2022.

Paper Type: Descriptive and Analytical Research.

Keywords: Home-based business, Bootstrapping homepreneurs, micro-scale business sector, digital transformation marketing strategies, input-output model, validity, reliability.

JEL Classification: B21, C67, C83, C88, L86

1. INTRODUCTION:

Various macroeconomic variables such as national income, consumption, saving, investment, employment, and so on are used to analyze economic performance. In July 1991, the Government of India initiated economic reforms in various sectors of the economy, gaining control of national income and people's standard of living. However, the current pandemic crisis has replaced revolution in the Indian economic motif, and one major upshot of this current pandemic predicament is the addition of the concept "Homepreneur," which is also considered a noun drastic change in disintegrating the stereotypes of old business concepts [1]. In today's competitive business environment, businesses are

expanding into homes and spawning homepreneurs. Home-based businesses are now recognized as an important component of the micro-scale business sector, resulting in an increased proportion of business start-ups. However, in the Indian economic motif, the current pandemic crisis has replaced revolution, and one major outcome of this current pandemic predicament is the addition of the concept "Homepreneur," which is also considered a noun drastic change in disintegrating the stereotypes of old business concepts. Businesses are expanding into homes and spawning homepreneurs in today's competitive business environment. Home-based businesses are now recognized as an important component of the micro-scale business sector, resulting in a higher proportion of new business ventures [2].

Technological advancements, particularly digitalization in the business world, have reimagined the term "homepreneur" in India. In this customer-challenging era, which has resulted in massive changes in customer purchasing behavioral patterns and technological integration, the concept of home-based businesses has reaped enormous consumer acceptance. The publicizing of e-commerce and social networking channels, has paved the way for the mutation of hobbies of people into home-based business ventures. In this context, the researcher tries to analyze the relationship between various aspects of digital transformation marketing strategies and their influence on Homepreneurs business practices in Mid- Kerala districts. This study focuses on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" who run online/virtual businesses in three Mid-Kerala districts: Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam. In this study, descriptive and analytical research designs were used. Demographic and primary data were collected using a standardized questionnaire distributed to 150 respondents doing online/virtual business in three Mid-Kerala districts. The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement. The data were analyzed using correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, the Multicollinearity test, and structural equation modelling.

The INPUT - OUTPUT model [3] was applied to data from 2021 to 2022 by the researcher. The study aims to assess the impact of digital transformation marketing strategies on homepreneur business practices in three districts of Kerala's central region. Since digital marketing is one of the recent emerging trends and is having a lot of applications in various areas, this study tries to attempt its various applications with special reference to "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" in Mid- Kerala by conducting a primary survey using a multi-stage cluster sampling method.

The remaining of this paper is organized into six sections. Section 2 defines the problem statement, Section 3 discusses the literature review, Section 4 discusses research methodology, Section 5 presents "empirical results and analysis," and Section 6 concludes the study.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Today, home-based businesses have an intrinsic portrayal in the small business sector and account for an increasing proportion of business start-ups, particularly during times of emergency/pandemic situations around the world. Especially in this current pandemic scenario, where the entire high society has been in the worst situation for the past three years, it is very relevant to study those business individuals who made the best of their resources to make a better living by making investments in technological advancements in an effective and efficient manner. This entrepreneurial behavioral pattern leaves a mark on their entire entrepreneurial career. It is important to understand how businesspeople differentiated the concept of a workspace from the traditional pattern of a formal working environment while also disregarding gender, religion, age, educational qualification, and so on. When the entire country was experiencing very adverse conditions such as lockdowns, restrictions on people's movements in society, and so on, it is important to know how people could generate their livelihood by setting up their own home-based business ventures, which appears to be a game changer as our economy demands innovative, effective, and efficient ventures that could contribute to the country's economic growth. Thus, in this context, the researcher discovers the topic of Homepreneur Emergence, particularly "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" and digital transformation marketing strategies in mid-districts of Kerala [4].

3. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Pooja Srivastava * and Meenal Sharma (2020) [5] published in their study comprehends and investigates the concept of homepreneurs in India, identifies the distinguishing characteristics of homepreneurs and their businesses, and addresses the level of digitalization in home-based businesses, its consequences, and the formulation of a future agenda. Home-based online business ventures are a growing but under-researched phenomenon. The study improves business people's experiences, understanding, and mindset for establishing and running such enterprises.

Faradillah Iqmar, Omar et al. (2020) [6] has conducted a study which explains the role of digital marketing in promoting the brand of business products through all forms of digital advertising mediums as a more interactive and informative alternative.

Tsonatsa Bodoine (2020) [7] reported in his PhD thesis emphasis that marketing has been a major challenge for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) worldwide due to high costs. The traditional marketing communication system, such as television, radio, and so on, appears to have a high cost for which it does not even reach the targeted customers, resulting in the expected result. The purpose of this research was to assess the impact of digital marketing on the growth of SMEs in Cameroon.

Lucina Priyadarshini Rout, et al (2021) [1] have conducted a study on "An Empirical Study on the Effect of Digitalization on Homepreneurs". In this study, Homepreneurs are independent and empowered by different tools, techniques and online platforms. In this paper, researchers try to study about the concept of Homepreneur and analyze the effect of digital transformation on them. This research tries to provide an insight into the real effect of digitalization on Homepreneurs at grass root level.

In the research report titled "The Effect of Digital Marketing on SMEs," Abdulrazak Taiye Arobo (2022) [8] attempts to investigate the value and impact of digital marketing on the competitive participation of small and medium-sized businesses in the business environment. The study would also look into whether digital marketing can have a significant impact on SMEs' consistent growth and success, improve brand recognition, and strengthen customer relationships. Although there has been a related study on social media as it impacts innovation and creativity in SMEs, it indicates that social media can be a very positive strategy for companies that operate within the context of small and medium-scale Enterprises.

In their research article, Ali Meshman, et al (2022) [9] focused on the Service of SMEs at present, which is characterized by intense competition and quick changes in client expectations, improving regulatory standards, technological innovation, and increased competition.

4. RESEARCH GAP:

The researcher chooses the research title "Impact of Digital Transformation Marketing Strategies on Homepreneur Business Practices in Kerala" for the study because only limited research studies was found with relation to this area. Various studies based on challenges and opportunities of homepreneur business, digital marketing strategies and their applications in homepreneur business, etc, has been conducted, but only limited studies were conducted which have been focused on digital transformation marketing strategies on homepreneur business with special reference to "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" and how technological advancements like digital marketing can be explored for promoting "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- (1) To investigate the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on the business practices of "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs."
- (2) To explore the interconnection between digital transformation marketing strategies and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.
- (3) To develop a Conceptual Model to inter-relate the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on the business practices of "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs."
- (4) To prove the Conceptual Model through an empirical study by developing and testing the hypotheses.
- (5) To update/finalize the conceptual model using accepted hypotheses.
- (6) To provide recommendations based on proven models related to the research problem considered.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

6.1 Conceptual Model Development:

This study paper discusses how digital marketing transformation tactics can be applied to improve the practices of homepreneurs. Digital communication, transparency, investment return, customer relationship, digital advertisement, and visibility are all facets of digital marketing transformation strategies (independent variables) that are closely related to homepreneur company practices. Ruchi Gupta and Kiran Nair (2021) [10] established a conceptual model that demonstrates how digital platforms have boosted entrepreneurship promotion. However, parts of digital marketing techniques may have an impact on homepreneur company practices (depending on the variable). Figure 1 depicts a conceptual model that will be used to guide future statistical assessments of the correlations between these factors.

6.2 Postulates for Conceptual Model:

- (1) Digital communication has an impact on bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.
- (2) Transparency has an effect on bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.
- (3) Investment return has an influence on bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.
- (4) Customer relationship affects the business practices of bootstrapping homepreneurs.
- (5) Digital advertisements have an influence on bootstrapping homepreneurs' business practices.
- (6) Visibility/Exposure has an impact on bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.

6.3 Conceptual Model:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model developed

Discussion on Conceptual model to relate various factors and their implication:

The conceptual model for the influence of digital transformation marketing strategies on homepreneur business practices (Figure 1) depicts how the various elements of a digital marketing strategy (digital communication, transparency, return on investment, customer relationship, digital advertisements, and visibility/exposure) and their relationship with the business practices of bootstrapping homepreneurs are related. This model is based on the Input-Output model (Michal Przybylinski and Artur Gorzalczyński, 2022) [11].

Let us now investigate the links between the dependent and independent variables in this conceptual model. In today's digital age, digital communication has become an important digital marketing technique. It has the power to enhance revenue, create brands, and drive site traffic to connect customers via various social media platforms (Rifki Hanif 2019) [12]. A recent study in this area has yielded promising outcomes in terms of corporate expansion. Kristina Kundeliene and Sviesa Leitonisne (2015) [13] concluded their study by highlighting possibilities of business information transparency and they analysed its influence on business practices in terms of reliability, clarity, timeliness etc. and they concluded their study stating that these variables are having a significant influence on the business activities of various organisations. Various digital marketing tactics, such as pay-per-click, websites, email marketing, and so on, can lower the cost of business practices and hence have a favourable impact on company practices in terms of return on investment (Ali Akeel and Manisha Gubbain 2020) [14]. Digital marketing techniques attempt to build brand awareness, generate leads, and increase sales by connecting with potential customers online and hence have a positive association with various business practices. As part of a one-to-many approach in digital marketing, businesses frequently generate content or campaigns for a large audience (A. Lavanya) [15]. Balmer John M T (2008) [16] examined the impact of online advertisements on business performance in her study paper. According to the study, digital advertisements have a big impact on company practices such as brand image building, increased sales, broad market reach, and so on. Customers may readily study products and services through digital marketing channels such as websites and social media, which increases the visibility of business organizations and their business practices. The research studies suggest that visibility and business practices have a strong relationship with the visibility aspect of digital marketing (2018, Asia R Lockett) [17].

Thus, various elements of digital marketing strategies can improve the business practices of various homepreneurs and various research studies have demonstrated that there is a positive impact of various aspects of digital marketing strategies towards homepreneur business practices with regards to digital communication transparency, investment return, customer relationship, digital advertisements, and visibility/exposure

6.4 Hypothesis to Test Conceptual Model:

H1: Digital communication and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices have a beneficial association.

H2: Transparency and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" operations constitute a beneficial connection.

H3: Investment return and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities have a positive relationship.

H4: Relationships with customers and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" operational processes do have a positive relationship.

H5: Digital advertisement strategy along with targeting new strategy and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities have a significant relationship.

H6: Visibility/exposure and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" ways of doing business have a positive relationship.

H7: Digital transformation marketing strategies has a positive influence on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.

6.5 Data and Sources of Data for Hypotheses Testing:

This study used both quantitative and qualitative data from primary and secondary data sources to investigate the influence of digital transformation marketing techniques on homepreneur businesses.

A standardized questionnaire was used to collect demographic and primary data from one hundred and fifty (150) respondents. These respondents under the study are the “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” doing online/virtual business from three districts of Mid-Kerala, namely **Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam**.

The study's data focuses on the factors that influence the effectiveness of digital transformation marketing strategies on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices, as well as attempting to identify the interrelationships between digital transformation marketing strategies and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.

In addition, the sample selection parameters have been updated as follows:

- (1) The entire Kerala state has been divided into North, South, and Mid-Kerala zones
- (2) Out of the three zones the respondents from three districts of Mid -Kerala (Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam) have been chosen as samples for collecting the data.
- (3) From each Mid-Kerala district 50 respondents have been selected as samples for the study.

The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were used to confirm the study's validity and reliability, as well as the variables of measurement [18].

7. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS :

7.1 Reliability Test:

Table 1 demonstrates that Cronbach's Alpha is 0.774, implying that the questionnaire's reliability is moderately good.

Table 1: Statistics on Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items, Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
.774	.774	25

Validity analysis

The data was validated by using the KMO measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The KMO test result is 0.787. It clearly shows that the KMO statistics value is greater than 0.7, indicating that the data might be beneficial for further analysis.

7.2 Correlation analysis:

Table 2: Correlation analysis test result

S. No.	Hypotheses	Coefficient of correlation	Interpretation
1	Digital communication and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices have a beneficial association.	0.585	Moderate positive correlation
2	Investment return and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities have a positive relationship.	0.665	Moderate positive correlation
3	Relationships with customers and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" operational processes do have a positive relationship	0.783	High positive correlation
4	Transparency and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" operations constitute a beneficial connection	0.705	Moderate positive correlation
5	There is a positive relationship between visibility /exposure and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices	0.623	Moderate positive correlation
6	Digital advertisement strategy along with targeting new strategy and "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities have a significant relationship.	0.575	Moderate positive correlation

The correlation evaluation of different components of digital transformation strategies and Bootstrapping Homepreneur marketing practices is presented in the table above. Pearson To ascertain the relationship between the variables, the correlation coefficient was calculated. As per Correlation Analysis, there is a solid and modestly strong positive relationship between various aspects of digital transformation strategies and Bootstrapping Homepreneur operational processes.

7.3 Multiple Regression Analysis:

H0. Digital transformation marketing strategies have a positive influence on “Bootstrapping Homepreneurs” business practices.

Table 3: Model Summary: Determinants of Digital Marketing Strategies on Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.731 ^a	.535	.526	1.92124

Predictors: Digital communication, transparency, return on investment, customer relationship, remarketing/retargeting, visibility/exposure.

Source: Primary Data

The above table 3 indicates that the estimation of R Square equals.535, denoting that 53.5percent of the variability in the influence level of various aspects of the digital transformation marketing strategies (digital communication, transparency, return on investment, customer relationship, remarketing/retargeting, visibility/exposure) towards "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities are largely attributable to "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs." The use of adjusted R2 resulted in a revised estimate that 52.6% of the discrepancies in the influence level of the digital transformation marketing strategies in the study is explained by six independent variables.

Table 4: Multicollinearity Coefficient Analysis: Determinants of Digital Marketing Strategies on Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.645	1.656		.993	.321		
Return on investment	.279-3	.125	.221	2.232	.006	.154	6.505
Remarketing/Retargeting	.056-6	.057	.050	-.978	.009	.570	1.754
Customer relationship	.953-1	.085	.649	11.239	.000	.453	2.205
Digital communication	.090-5	.135	.072	.666	.006	.129	7.759
Visibility/Exposure	.095-4	.055	.083	1.710	.008	.633	1.579
Transparency	.648-2	.119	.270	-5.450	.000	.617	1.620

Dependent variable: **Bootstrapping Homepreneur business Practices**

Return on investment (.279), Customer relationship (.953), Digital communication (.090), Visibility and exposure (.095), Transparency (.648), and Remarketing and Retargeting (.056) all are positively related "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business tactics, according to the above coefficients table 4.

Customer relationships (.649) have a bigger effect on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business activities. The results indicate that independent variables such as return on investment, remarketing and retargeting, digital communication, visibility/exposure, and transparency have such a substantial effect on the business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs [18-21]. The significant value shows that all variables had an impact on the business practices of Bootstrapping Homepreneurs. The effect of multicollinearity is excluded because the model includes all of the predicted variables, including transparency, visibility and exposure, return on investment, remarketing and retargeting, customer relationship, and digital communication.

8. FINAL UPDATED CONCEPTUAL MODEL :

Fig. 2: Accepted conceptual model

9. ABCD LISTING ON ACCEPTED MODEL :

Analysis of research results refers to the process of examining and interpreting gathered information or developed conceptual models. It is essential to analyze the developed conceptual model for its use in solving similar types of problems. In this section, we have analyzed the use of the newly developed conceptual model. There are many analysis frameworks used in scholarly research which include SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis [22], PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis [23], and ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis [24]. The advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the developed model are listed here as per ABCD analysis framework [25-27].

(A) Advantages:

Various benefits of the company strategy must be outlined under common factors such as Technological Advantages are made up of two factors: the breadth of use of technology and the degree of reliance on technology in bootstrapping homepreneurs' business practices. Digital communication, transparency, investment return, customer relationship, digital advertisements, and visibility/exposure are some of the technical advantages.

(B) Benefits:

Various advantages of the business model must be listed under common components of technological advantages. These factors' constituent attributes as business benefits must be identified and investigated. The following characteristics of bootstrapping homepreneur business ~~practices~~, represent technological benefits: increased reachability, higher sales and sales revenues, increased market size, and business ~~practise~~ expansion.

(C) Constraints:

Various business model constraints must be listed under a common factor, Technological constraint. These factors' constituent attributes as bootstrapping homepreneurs business constraints must be ~~recognised~~ and assessed. The business factors evaluated in the domain of technology restrictions include automation installation costs, security breaches, and a lack of digital knowledge and capabilities.

(D) Disadvantages:

Various drawbacks of the business model must be classified under a common aspect of technological drawbacks. Disconnection, diversions, cybercrime, and cost are all business deployment considerations that are covered in technology drawbacks. Commercial organizations must evaluate their disadvantages in light of the aforementioned variables and attempt to convert those difficulties into commercial opportunities in order to remain competitive.

10. MAJOR FINDINGS :

- (1) From the correlation analysis it has been found that there is a moderate and high correlation between various factors such as digital communication, return on investment, customer relationship, transparency, visibility/exposure, remarketing/retargeting, and bootstrapping homepreneur business practices.
- (2) The most influential factor out of various aspects of digital marketing strategies towards bootstrapping homepreneur business practices is customer relationship (0.783).
- (3) Digital transformation marketing strategies have a positive influence on "Bootstrapping Homepreneurs" business practices.
- (4) All the determinants of digital transformation marketing strategies are statistically independent.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS :

- (1) In order to improve digital communication, visibility/exposure, it is recommended to follow certain internet marketing techniques such as SEO promotion, Email-mailing list, contextual advertising, ~~etc~~, rather than focusing more on social media advertising.
- (2) It is highly recommended to create websites for Bootstrapping Homepreneurs and also has to utilize various digital channels such as Search Engine Optimization, Video marketing, influencer marketing, ~~etc~~ in order to reduce the cost and thereby contribute towards a satisfactory return on investment.
- (3) Geotargeting strategy can be adopted in order to develop an effective and efficient digital communication system among Bootstrapping Homepreneurs and consumers.

12. CONCLUSIONS :

Digital transformation marketing strategies are based on the most frequently used internet channels, which are dynamic, changing from year to year, and always influenced by market trends. In terms of effective customer relationship management, digital communication, exposure, visibility, cost and revenue management, and so on, various aspects of digital marketing strategies have a positive impact on bootstrapping homepreneur business practices. The impact of this type of unconventional marketing on homepreneur business practices around the world has been enormous. As a result, it is demonstrated that a number of different aspects of digital marketing have had a significant influence on the business practices of bootstrapping homepreneurs in the formation and development of the business structure: (1) Keeping in touch with customers via digital marketing communication techniques: This procedure can be carried out using a set of Internet marketing techniques aimed at targeting customers through a specific type of information and managing customer relationships through various digital communication strategies such as SEO - promotion, Email - mailing list, contextual advertising, social network advertising, and so on. (2) Visibility, Exposure, and Transparency: Digital marketing strategies

result in the emergence of e-commerce, which at times facilitates the process of purchasing goods and services because purchases are made through online stores, resulting in cost-effectiveness and increased sales because all necessary information is available on digital platforms; (3) Return on investment: Internet marketing implies an effective mechanism for bringing the product to consumers through virtual targeting, but it is a budgetary one in use because the majority of the work is done directly on the Internet by a small number of employees.

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An Assessment of Green Marketing Tools and Strategies for Increasing the Consumption Pattern of Khadi Textile Products Among Millennials in Kerala

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The challenge for policymakers in Kerala today is to effectively and efficiently manage the twin themes of economic development while minimizing environmental damage. During this context, the predominance of green products and green marketing methods and strategies (eco packaging, green branding, green advertising, green labelling, and environmental belief) gains important. Green marketing is a phenomenon that has gained prominence in the current market. Green or ecological marketing is technically a method of producing and advertising goods and services based on their positive effects on the long-term environment and societal advantages. The commodities created are thought to be environmentally friendly and safe for consumption, hence they are referred to as Green Products. The new green movements must reach the public, which will take a significant amount of time and effort. Yoga and natural food intake are examples of healthy living practices that Kerala consumers are exposed to. In those areas, consumers are already aware and would be willing to accept green products such as handlooms and Khadi not just in Kerala but both nationally and globally. These are "Green Products" because they are environmentally sustainable. This study aims to explore the relationship between various features of green marketing techniques and how they affect the consumption rate of Khadi textile products in the districts of mid Kerala.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The population of the study is made up of "Khadi textile consumers" from three districts in Mid-Kerala: Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam. The descriptive and analytical research designs were used in this study. A standardized questionnaire was used to obtain demographic and primary data from 150 respondents using a multi-stage cluster sampling procedure. The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were utilized to validate the study's validity and reliability, as well as the measurement variables. Correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, the Multicollinearity test, one sample T-test, and structural equation modelling were used to assess the data. The study aims to evaluate the interplay between various components of green marketing techniques and tactics, as well as how they influence the consumption behaviour of Khadi textile customers in Kerala, with a focus on the Mid - Kerala region.*

Findings/Result: *According to the findings of the analysis, various aspects of green marketing tools and strategies have a positive influence on the consumption pattern of Khadi textile consumers, and all determinants of green marketing tools and strategies are statistically independent.*

Originality/Value: *The researcher applied INPUT – OUTPUT model to the data from 2022 to 2023.*

Paper Type: *Descriptive and Analytical Research.*

Keywords: Green products, Green marketing tools and strategies, Environment-friendly, Ecological marketing, Input-output model, Validity, Reliability, Khadi Textile Products

1. INTRODUCTION:

Green marketing [1] refers to the promotion of ecologically friendly [2] products and services. It includes product/service alteration, improvements to the manufacturing/packaging process, and promotion. Green marketing is carefully incorporating social and environmental considerations into the relationship between the firm and the client. Green marketing, as opposed to traditional marketing, which uses outgoing marketing (television advertising, print advertising, direct mail, and telemarketing) and focuses on push methods, employs inbound marketing, which focuses on pull strategies. This procedure necessitates a holistic strategy because businesses must naturally integrate all activities in accordance with environmental considerations. In today's economic context, where reliance on foreign capital and know-how is expanding all over, the Khadi sector offers a sustainable form of economic activity that is not dependent on foreign capital and know-how. The link between marketing practises and customer consumption patterns is important in improving the business performance of Khadi textile industry. As a result, it is critical that Khadi bhavans in Kerala strive to establish and sustain consumer satisfaction and loyalty. In order to compete in a competitive market, the Khadi textile sector is focusing on the client. It is commonly known that acquiring a new customer costs four to five times more than retaining an existing one. Furthermore, an unhappy customer causes business damage because they are more likely to defect to competitors and are more easily persuaded to defect others. As a result, it is not surprising that marketing practise is a hot topic in today's commercial world. The formation of an appealing link between Khadi textile businesses' marketing practises and consumers is the key to ensuring a better level of consumer loyalty. Because Khadi textile products are classified as green products, it is important to comprehend the implications of green marketing practises in the Khadi textile sector, given the growing importance of green marketing practises around the world. Individuals' green purchase intentions were shown to be incremental as their degree of education increased. Green marketing tactics such as environmental belief, green packaging, green branding, green advertisement, and green labelling have been studied to determine their impact on consumer purchase intentions. This research study focuses on green marketing strategies and how they influence favourable purchasing intentions towards Khadi textile products, as well as their varied applications in producing major improvements in the consumption pattern of Khadi textile customers [3].

In this context, the researcher attempts to examine the relationship between various components of green marketing tactics and their impact on consumption behaviour of Khadi textile consumers [4] in the districts of Mid-Kerala. The researcher chooses the research title "An Assessment of Green Marketing Tools for Increasing the Consumption Pattern of Khadi Textile Products Among Millennials in Kerala" for the study because only limited research studies was found with relate to this area. Various studies based on challenges and opportunities of Khadi textile business, green marketing strategies and its applications in various sectors, etc, has been conducted, but only limited studies were conducted which has been focused on green marketing tools and strategies and how it is influencing on the consumption pattern Khadi textile consumers with special reference to Millennials in three mid-Kerala districts. This study focuses on Khadi textile customers in three districts in Kerala's Mid-Kerala region: Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam. The descriptive and analytical research designs were used in this study. A standardized questionnaire was issued to 150 respondents running online/virtual business in three Mid-Kerala districts to collect demographic and primary data. The pilot survey and Cronbach's Alpha were utilized to validate the study's validity and reliability, as well as the measurement variables. Descriptive analysis, Correlation analysis, multiple regression analysis, the Multicollinearity test, ANOVA test, T test, and structural equation modelling were used to assess the data.

The researcher used the INPUT - OUTPUT model [5] on data from 2022 to 2023. The study's goal is to evaluate the impact of green marketing techniques and tactics on the consumption patterns of Khadi cloth consumers in three districts in Kerala's central region. Because green marketing tools and strategies are a recent emerging trend with many applications in various areas, this study attempts to attempt its influence with special reference to "Khadi textile consumer's" consumption behaviour patterns in Mid-Kerala by conducting a primary survey using a multi-stage cluster sampling method.

The rest of this work is divided into five sections. Section 2 addresses the literature review; Section 3 explains research methodology; Section 4 gives "empirical results and analysis"; and Section 5 closes the study.

2. RELATED WORKS:

2.1. Green Marketing Tools and Strategies:

The technique of employing eco-friendly paper and inks for print marketing materials is known as green marketing strategy. Electronic marketing is replacing printed goods entirely. Adopting garbage disposal practises that are environmentally responsible. Product packaging made from eco-friendly or recycled materials. Companies can practise green marketing by manufacturing their products with environmentally friendly components. This can include employing recycled materials or other eco-friendly materials, such as product packaging that is biodegradable.

Table 1: Review of Green marketing tools and strategies

S. No.	Green marketing tools and strategies	Focus	Reference
1	Green Marketing Strategies: Theoretical Approach	Concerns regarding the theoretical approach of green marketing tactics and consumers' behavioural intention to purchase green products.	Akram Mohamad Alhamad, et al. (2019). [6]
2	Green Marketing Strategies: An examination of stakeholders and opportunities they present	The interconnected nature of marketing, management (both strategy and human resources), and operations as controllable aspects inside an organisation from which strategies can be adopted to affect a firm's stakeholders is addressed. The interconnected nature of marketing, management (both strategy and human resources), and operations as controllable activities within an organisation from which strategies can be adopted to affect a firm's stakeholders	Joseph Cronin J, et al. (2011). [7]
3	Green Marketing Strategies, Environmental Attitude, and Green Buying Intention: A Multi-Group Analysis in an Emerging Economy Context	The relationship between green marketing mix techniques and green purchasing intents of consumers (millennials) in an emerging economy towards green personal care items, as well as the impact of green marketing methods on this.	Balveen Kaur, et al. (2022). [8]

2.2. Green Marketing Tools And Strategies for increasing the consumption pattern:

Green marketing tactics are business strategies used to promote and sell environmentally friendly products and services. These initiatives seek to enhance consumer knowledge about the environmental impact of their shopping decisions and to encourage sustainable consumption practices.

Table 2: Review of Green marketing tools and strategies for increasing the consumption pattern

S. No.	Green marketing tools and strategies for increasing the consumption pattern	Focus	Reference
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1	The impact of green marketing strategies on consumer purchasing patterns in Mauritius	The prospect of incorporating greener consumption patterns into modern lifestyles at an era when green products are becoming more widely available.	Jyoti, Thanika Devi, et al. (2012). [9]
2	Green Marketing and its impact on consumer behavior	Green Marketing's Influence on Consumer Behaviour.	Syeda Shazia Bukhari, (2011). [10]
3	Green Marketing Tools towards Consumer Purchase Intention in Kathmandu	The impact of green marketing tools on product selection and how green initiatives influence consumer buy intention, as well as the relationship between age, income, education, and employment and consumer purchase intention in combination with green marketing tools.	Shuloy, Shrestha, (2022). [11]

2.3. Green Marketing Tools and Strategies for increasing the consumption pattern of Khadi Textile Products:

Green or ecological marketing is technically a method of producing and advertising goods and services based on their positive environmental impacts and societal advantages. The commodities created are deemed environmentally friendly as well as safe for consumption, and as a result, they are suitably referred to as Green Products. It is critical to determine the products that can be labelled as "Green." It is the marketing or sale of a product or service based on its environmental benefits. Because of their eco-friendliness, Khadi textile products are considered green products.

Table 3: Review of Green marketing tools and strategies for increasing the consumption pattern Of Khadi Textile Products:

S. No.	Green marketing tools and strategies for increasing the consumption pattern Of Khadi Textile Products	Focus	Reference
1	Green marketing strategy for empowering handloom industries.	Handloom product characteristics, the impact of green marketing on handloom items, and its strengths and weaknesses in the Indian market.	Veena R. Humbe, (2012). [12]
2	The effects of consumer attitude on green purchase intention: A meta-analytic path analysis	Integrate the model of green purchasing behaviour (GPB) and the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) meta-analytically.	Zeinab Zaremohzzabieh, et al. (2021). [13]
3	Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Khadi Fashion Wear	Khadi Bhandars offering Khadi fashion wear products, as well as the factors that influence consumer purchasing behaviour for Khadi products.	Dibyendu Bikash Datta1, Biswajit Sarkar, (2022). [14]

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:-

(1) To research the elements that determine the effectiveness of green marketing strategies on Khadi textile customers' purchasing patterns.

- (2) To investigate the relationship between green marketing techniques and Khadi textile customers' consumption patterns.
- (3) To create a conceptual model that interrelates the aspects that determine the success of green marketing tools on Khadi cloth customers' purchase patterns.
- (4) To prove a conceptual model that interrelates the aspects that influence the success of green marketing tools and tactics on the consumption patterns of Khadi textile customers.
- (5) To update/finalize the conceptual model using accepted hypotheses.
- (6) To provide recommendations based on proven model related to research problem.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

This research paper examines how green marketing tactics might be used to enhance the consumption habits of Khadi cloth customers. The method by which an individual plans future purchases of goods and services is known as the consumer consumption pattern. It is the sum of a consumer's attitude, choice, and decision regarding marketplace behaviour. Purchase intention is defined as a situation where a consumer tends to buy a certain product in certain condition [15]. Purchase behaviour is a key point for consumers to access and evaluate a specific product. This study analyses the effect on the purchase/consumption intention of consumers considering the use of green marketing tools.

5. FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONSUMPTION PATTERN OF CONSUMERS :

A comprehensive model was developed on the premise of a research paper presented by Shuloy Shrestha "Analysis of Green Marketing Tools towards Consumer Purchase Intention in Kathmandu" [11]. The model shows green marketing as the independent variable, consisting of five major aspects such as environmental belief, green packaging, green branding, green advertising, and green labelling which influences the consumer's intention to purchase. Other factors such as age, occupation, gender, price, income and education act as moderating variables.

Table 4: Components of Independent variables and their important characteristic elements

S. No.	Components of Independent Variables	Characteristic elements
1	Environmental Belief	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmental concerns 2. Values 3. Attitudes
2	Green Packaging	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Light weight raw materials 2. Reusage 3. Recycling 4. Rethinking conventional norms and expectations of packaging
3	Eco/Green Labelling	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Specific environmental standards 2. Advertise environmental quality 3. Initiative to address the problem of environmental deterioration
4	Green Branding	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmentally friendly in production 2. Co-responsibility for the conservation of natural resources and are highly committed to the preservation and balance of nature and sustainability.
5.	Green Advertising	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adopting sustainable business practices 2. Creating eco-friendly products 3. Implementing eco-friendly packaging 4. Communicating the environmental benefits of the product.

5.1 Postulates for Conceptual Model:

- (1) Environmental belief has impact on Khadi textile consumers' consumption pattern.
- (2) Green packaging has effect on Khadi textile consumers' consumption pattern.

- (3) Green branding has influence on Khadi textile consumers' consumption pattern.
- (4) Green advertising affects the consumption pattern of Khadi textile consumers.
- (5) Green labelling has influence on Khadi textile consumers' consumption pattern.

5.2 Conceptual Model:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model developed

5.3 Discussion on Conceptual model to relate various factors and their implication:

Environmental Belief: Environmental beliefs influence how people act in favour of or against the environment (M. Carmen Aguilar-Luzón, 2020) [16]. Furthermore, consumer values correspond to broad guiding concepts in people's lives (Thijs Bouman et al 2018) [17]. Human behaviour is guided by three types of considerations, according to the Theory of Planned Behaviour: beliefs about the likely consequences of the behaviour (behavioural beliefs), beliefs about the normative expectations of others (normative beliefs), and beliefs about the presence of factors that may facilitate or impede behaviour performance (control beliefs) (Bosnjak M 2020) [18]. The Structural Equation Model (SEM) can be used to demonstrate the effect of environmental concern, attitudes, and behaviours on environmentally conscious purchasing behaviour (Talha Arslan et al 2012) [19].

Green Packaging: Green packaging—also known as 'eco-green packaging,' 'eco-friendly packaging,' 'sustainable packaging,' or 'recyclable packaging'—uses ecological materials for packaging purposes while keeping in mind that products must be effective and safe for human health and the environment (Pauer, E 2019) [20]. Sustainable development is a global goal that seeks to address societal challenges such as climate change, the environment, resource efficiency, and raw resources. In this regard, promoting green packaging, that is, the use of sustainable materials and designs for goods packaging, is a crucial strategy (Dr. Gonzalo Wandosell, 2021) [21]. Environmentally friendly packaging is critical for increasing favourable attitudes and patronage intentions towards consumer purchasing intentions (Madalyn Smith, 2015) [22].

Eco/Green Labelling: Ecolabels are regarded as an excellent marketing and advertising technique that informs modern consumers about a product's green attributes. They present information that encourages consumers to have a favourable attitude and really purchase green products (Dr. Kyriakos Riskos et al.

(2021). [23]). To promote a product or service with an eco and/or social label, certain label-specific requirements must be met, and certification must typically be gained through a specified process (Nicole Bahlmann (2018). [24].

Green Branding: Green branding may utilise the eco-market through eco-labelling and eco-foot printing, which are complemented by green supply chain management practices. The consequences of green branding are well established, and increasing green consumer purchasing behaviour supports this scenario. Its varied consequences include a rise in demand for existing and new green products, a movement in consumer preference to greener brands within a category, a positive view of green brands, and so on. (Sarkar, A. N. (2012) [25]).

Green Advertising: Green advertising represents an effective communication means to influence consumers' attitudes and behaviour, even though its effectiveness is often mediated by certain factors, like: consumers' environmental consciousness, consumers' regulatory focus, etc. Green advertising effectiveness is necessary in order to stimulate cognitive and affective reactions of consumers to green advertisements, as well as their subsequent environmentally friendly behaviour (Jelena Krstić, et al. 2021). [26].

6. HYPOTHESIS TO TEST CONCEPTUAL MODEL.:

H1: There is no positive correlation between environmental belief and Khadi textile consumer buying trend.

H2: There is no favourable relationship between green labelling and Khadi textile consumer purchase patterns.

H3: Green branding and Khadi brand image have no significant association.

H4: There is no significant association between green advertising and Khadi textile consumer buying patterns.

H5: There is no substantial association between green packaging and Khadi textile consumer purchase patterns.

H6: Green marketing tactics and tools have a favourable impact on the buying habits of "Khadi textile consumers."

7. DATA AND SOURCES OF DATA FOR HYPOTHESIS TESTING.:

This study investigated the impact of green marketing tactics on the consumption patterns of Khadi textile customers using both quantitative and qualitative data from primary and secondary data sources. This study examined the influence of green marketing tactics on the purchase patterns of Khadi textile customers using both quantitative and qualitative data from primary and secondary data sources. The study and data focus on the factors that influence the effectiveness of green marketing tools and strategies, as well as attempting to identify the interrelationships between green marketing strategies/tools and Khadi textile consumers' consumption behaviour.

In addition, the sample selection parameters have been updated as follows:

(1) Kerala has been separated into three zones: North, South, and Mid-Kerala.

(2) Of the three zones, respondents from three districts in Mid-Kerala (Palakkad, Thrissur, and Ernakulam) were chosen as samples for data collection.

(3) Fifty respondents were chosen as samples for the study from each Mid-Kerala district.

The pilot survey and Cronbach & Alpha were used to validate the study's validity and reliability, as well as the measurement variables [27].

8. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.:

8.1 Reliability Test:

Table 1 demonstrates that Cronbach's Alpha is 0.774, implying that the questionnaire's reliability is moderately good.

Validity analysis:

The data was validated by using the KMO measure and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The KMO test result is 0.789. It clearly shows that the KMO statistics value is greater than 0.7, indicating that the data might be beneficial for further analysis.

Table 5: Statistics on Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items, Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.776	0.776	25

8.2 General Profile of Respondents:

The general profile of respondents is mentioned in the table below:

Table 6: Summary of Demographic Variables

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES		PERCENTAGE
GENDER	MALE	47%
	FEMALE	53%
TOTAL		100%
OCCUPATION	EMPLOYED	38%
	SELF-EMPLOYED	12%
	STUDENT	32%
	HOMEMAKER	18%
TOTAL		100%
AGE GROUP	26-35	25%
	36-45	31%
	46-55	32%
	>55	12%
	TOTAL	100%
INCOME LEVEL	0-12000	12%
	12001-25000	26%
	25001-40000	44%
	>40000	18%
TOTAL		100%

Descriptive Statistics:

According to the report, people are more enthused about Khadi textile items and are drawn to them because they are classified as green products. Their willingness to spend a little extra on Khadi textile products as green products was influenced by their notion of contributing to environmental sustainability. Product kind, package, availability, and product visibility were discovered to be equally essential in influencing consumer consumption patterns. Despite the several Khadi product categories available, Khadi textile products were the most favoured green buy category.

Environmental belief was discovered to be a significant source of positive reinforcement motivating consumers to purchase environmentally friendly products (mean=1.91). Packaging not only drew people to green products but also assisted consumers in distinguishing them from ordinary items (mean=2.07). The majority of respondents deemed green-branded items trustworthy, indicating that green branding has a positive influence (mean=2.64). Advertisements also contributed to the propagation of green values and were recognised as a source of positive sway towards greener purchase intention (mean=1.96). Green labelling was found to be an essential strategy for influencing consumers' green buying intentions (mean=2.35).

8.3 Correlation analysis:

Table 7: Correlation analysis test result

S. No.	HYPOTHESIS	COEFFICIENT OF CORRELATION	INTERPRETATION
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1	Environmental belief and & Khadi textile consumer consumption pattern have no beneficial association.	.589	Moderate positive Correlation
2	Green labelling and & Khadi textile consumer consumption pattern <u>have</u> no beneficial connection.	.693	Moderate positive Correlation
3	There is no significant relationship between green branding and Khadi brand image	.758	High positive Correlation
4	Green advertising and & Khadi textile consumer consumption pattern have no significant relationship.	.618	Moderate positive Correlation
5	Green packaging and & Khadi textile consumer consumption pattern have no significant relationship.	.597	Moderate positive Correlation

The table above shows the correlation evaluation of key components of green marketing strategies and consumption patterns of Khadi textile customers. Pearson's calculated the correlation coefficient is to determine the link between the variables. According to Correlation Analysis, there is a solid and somewhat significant positive association between many components of green marketing techniques and Khadi textile customers' consumption patterns.

8.4 Multiple Regression Analysis:

H0. Green marketing strategies and tools have a positive influence on "Khadi textile consumers' consumption behaviour."

Table 8: Model Summary: Determinants of Green Marketing Tools and Strategies on Khadi textile consumers' consumption behaviour.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.733 ^a	.537	.528	1.92126

Predictors: Environmental belief, Green labelling, Green branding, Green advertisement, Green packag
Source: Primary Data.

The estimation of R Square equals .537 in the above table 8, indicating that 53.7 percent of the variability in the influence level of various aspects of green marketing tools and strategies (Environmental belief, green labelling, Green branding, Green advertisement, Green packaging) towards Khadi textile consumers' consumption behaviour is largely attributable to Khadi textile consumption. The use of adjusted R2 yielded a revised estimate that 52.8% of the differences in the influence level of the study's green marketing strategies and tools are explained by five independent variables.

Table 9: Multicollinearity Coefficient Analysis : Determinants of Green Marketing Tools and Strategies on Consumption behaviour of Khadi textile consumers

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Toleranc e	VIF
(Constant)	1.647	1.658		.995	.323		
Environmental belief	.094-5	.127	.223	2.234	.008	.156	6.507
Green labelling	.652-2	.121	.272	-5.452	.002	.619	1.622

Green Branding	.955-1	.087	.651	11.241	.002	.455	2.207
Green advertisement	.281-3	.137	.074	.668	.008	.131	7.761
Green Packaging	.097-4	.057	.085	1.712	.010	.635	1.581

Dependent variable: **Khadi textile consumer consumption behaviour**

According to the above coefficients Table 9, environmental belief (.094), green labelling (.651), green branding (.955), green advertisement (.281), and green packaging (.097) are all favourably connected to Khadi textile consumer consumption behaviour. Green branding (.651) has a greater impact on Khadi textile customer purchasing behaviour. The findings show that environmental beliefs, green labelling, green branding, green advertisement, and green packaging have a significant impact on Khadi textile consumer purchase behaviour. The significant value indicates that all variables influenced Khadi textile customer consumption behaviour. Because the model incorporates all of the anticipated variables, including Environmental belief, green labelling, green branding, green advertisement, and green packaging, the influence of multicollinearity can be eliminated.

8.5 One Sample T-Test between green marketing tools/strategies and Khadi textile consumer consumption decision:

A one sample T-test is a statistical process used to examine a distribution's mean value. It determines whether the sample mean differs from a known or hypothesised population mean statistically. The parametric One Sample T test was employed with the assumption that the sampled distribution is normal. Five study factors were tested. Green marketing methods and tactics were employed as an independent variable to demonstrate their impact on Khadi textile customer purchasing decisions.

Table 10: The test has been conducted using solely T-test and neither regression nor correlation has been done.

	Mean	Std Deviation	T	Sig	Remarks
Environmental belief	1.93	0.874	14.991	0.00	Significant
Green branding	2.66	0.927	-5.396	0.00	Significant
Green packaging	2.11	0.791	11.032	0.00	Significant
Green advertisement	1.98	0.774	13.152	0.00	Significant
Green labelling	2.39	0.891	-7.694	0.00	Significant

The study's findings were as expected, with green marketing aspects such as environmental belief, green labelling, green branding, green advertisement, and green packaging having a substantial impact on Khadi textile buyers' purchasing decisions. The belief in the environment (mean =1.93). This means that the majority of respondents believe that they consider the eco/environmental friendliness of products when making purchasing decisions. The significant result (p-value) is 0.00, which is less than 0.05 and indicates the statement's importance. The mean of green labelling (2.39) in relation to Khadi textile consumer buying decisions is less than 3. This suggests that the majority of respondents believe that green labelling influences Khadi textile consumer purchasing decisions and the significant value (p-value) is 0.00, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the statement is significant. The mean of the statement measuring green branding in relation to Khadi textile customer purchasing intention is less than three. As a result, most respondents regard Khadi textile products as credible green-branded items; yet, most customers believe that Khadi textile products actually satisfy the greening process. The p-value (significant value) is 0.00, which is less than 0.05, indicating that the assertion is significant. The

mean of the statement green advertisement and green packaging in relation to Khadi textile consumer consumption pattern is less than three. As a result, the majority of respondents think that green advertising and packaging pique their interest. Statements in these categories have a significant value (p-value) of 0.00, which is less than 0.05 and shows that the statement is significant.

9. FINAL UPDATED CONCEPTUAL MODEL :

Fig. 2: Accepted conceptual model

10. ABCD LISTING ON ACCEPTED MODEL :

The process of reviewing and interpreting acquired material or established conceptual models is referred to as research results analysis. It is critical to analyse the established conceptual model before applying it to comparable types of challenges. In this section, the researcher examined the application of a newly established conceptual model. In academic research, numerous analysis frameworks are employed, including the SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis [28], the PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis [29], and the ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis [30]. The created model's advantages, benefits, restrictions, and shortcomings are listed here in accordance with the ABCD analysis framework [31-32].

(A) Advantages:

The various advantages of the firm plan must be summarised under a common aspect such as green marketing tools and strategies advantages are comprised of two components: the varied uses of green marketing tools and the degree of reliance on green marketing tools and strategies. Some of the benefits of using green marketing methods and strategies include environmental belief, green labelling, green branding, green ads, and green packaging.

(B) Benefits:

Under common components of green marketing tools and strategies benefits, many advantages of the business model must be stated. Environmental advantages, product differentiation, cost savings, less investment, energy efficiency, and other features associated with green marketing tools and techniques have a favourable impact on customer purchasing decisions.

(C) Constraints:

Several business model restrictions must be classified under a common aspect, green marketing tools and tactics constraint. These element features must be detected and appraised as Khadi textile customer purchase decision restrictions. Greenwashing, navigating novelty, and optimising quality with sustainability are among the factors addressed in the arena of green marketing tools and strategies constraints.

(D) Disadvantages:

Various business model drawbacks must be classed under a common aspect of green marketing tools and strategies' downsides. Green marketing methods and strategies have significant investments in research and development, deceptive advertisements and false claims, large initial investments, and other downsides. In order to remain competitive, Khadi village industries must examine their shortcomings in light of the aforementioned criteria and strive to convert those obstacles into commercial opportunities.

11. MAJOR FINDINGS :

- (1) According to the correlation analysis, there is a moderate to high association between several aspects such as environmental belief, green labelling, green branding, green ads, green packaging, and Khadi textile customer consumption decisions.
- (2) Green branding (0.758) is the most influential component among the many features of green marketing tools and strategies on Khadi textile customer purchase decisions.
- (3) Green marketing methods and tools have a favourable impact on Khadi textile customer purchasing decisions.
- (4) All of the variables influencing green marketing tools and tactics are statistically independent.
- (5) Green marketing methods and tools have a considerable impact on Khadi textile customer purchasing decisions.

12. RECOMMENDATIONS :

- (1) It is highly suggested to support environmental initiatives such as conservative techniques, 'reuse' strategy, etc. and invest more in social media marketing in order to highlight Khadi textile items as green products.
- (2) It is highly recommended that the websites for Khadi and Village Industries be updated and that various digital channels such as Search Engine Optimisation, Video marketing, influencer marketing, and so on be used to reduce costs and thus contribute to a satisfactory return on investment.
- (3) To improve green labelling and packaging, it is strongly advised to add more product characteristics such as fabric type, materials used, location of manufacturing plant, website details, and so on, which aids consumers when making purchasing selections.

13. CONCLUSIONS :

The research focuses on the impact of green marketing strategies on Khadi textile customer purchasing decisions in three Mid Kerala regions. An examination of variables such as environmental belief, Eco-packaging and labelling, green branding, and green ads reveals that they have a positive and significant impact on the consumption intention of Khadi textile customers. Green branding was the most influential factor in Khadi cloth consumers' green consumption intentions. Furthermore, the majority of respondents acknowledged that they did check to see if the goods they were purchasing was environmentally friendly or not. The main finding of this article is that green-marketing strategies have a considerable impact on consumer intention to purchase Khadi textile products. According to the research, consumers in the Mid Kerala areas are interested in Khadi textile items. However, there is still a need to educate and teach consumers about the unique value addition of Khadi textile goods and how they differ from handloom and power loom textile products in Kerala. Khadi and Village Industries can afford green marketing techniques and tactics because they are part of the MSME sector and there is a high demand for eco-friendly and green products in the Kerala market. Because businesses are qualified for government subsidies, companies can offer refunds and discounts to encourage people with low incomes to buy Khadi Textile products. Once individuals acquire accustomed to the benefits (both

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